

H2020 DAEMON Project
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Deliverable 6.4

Final report on communication, dissemination and exploitation, and exploitation plan for after the project

Abstract

This deliverable summarizes the results attained by the project in year 3 and in the three-month extension of the DAEMON project in terms of dissemination and communication, standardization and open-source activities, exploitation and innovation. Moreover, it presents the exploitation plans of the consortium for after the project. Here we provide the list of executed activities in year 3 and the three months extension as well as the final overview on the targeted metrics.

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Disclaimer

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	9
2	Achievements in year 3.....	11
2.1	Communication activities.....	11
2.1.1	News and press releases.....	11
2.1.2	Web, social media and project communication material.....	12
2.2	Dissemination activities.....	15
2.2.1	Publications and technical dissemination.....	15
2.2.2	Synergies with other projects.....	23
2.3	Exploitation activities.....	25
2.3.1	Standardization activities.....	25
2.3.2	Open-source activities.....	27
2.3.3	Academic activities.....	29
2.3.4	Industrial exploitation activities.....	30
2.3.5	Event highlights.....	31
3	Communication, dissemination, exploitation KPIs over the whole project.....	36
3.1	Dissemination and communication activities.....	36
3.2	Exploitation activities.....	41
4	Exploitation plan for after the project.....	44
4.1	Exploitation plans for individual partners and project activities.....	44
4.1.1	Vendors and service providers.....	44
4.1.2	Network operators.....	45
4.1.3	Small and medium enterprises.....	45
4.1.4	Academic and research centers.....	46
4.2	Exploitation plan of products and platforms for vendors and SMEs.....	50
4.3	Exploitation plan for datasets and open-source software.....	52
4.3.1	End-of-project social media campaign.....	52
4.3.2	Legacy of the DAEMON NI Plane.....	52
4.3.3	NetMob 2023 Data Challenge dataset.....	53
4.3.4	Zenoh open-source software adoption initiatives.....	53
	References.....	54

List of Figures

Figure 1. DAEMON Dissemination & Exploitation Plan.	9
Figure 2. DAEMON Deliverable page on project website.	13
Figure 3. Total DAEMON website visits.	13
Figure 4. Google Analytics Report of most visited pages.....	13
Figure 5. Google Analytics Report of devices used to access DAEMON site.	14
Figure 6. Google Analytics Report of web-browsers used to access DAEMON site.	14
Figure 7. Google Analytics Report of DAEMON site demographics.	14
Figure 8. Twitter Analytics Report of tweets impressions and engagement of the last three months.	15
Figure 9. Official Profile of DAEMON on Twitter.....	15
Figure 10. Example of the Zenodo analytics for each published asset in the DAEMON community.	23
Figure 11. srsRAN Project Github star history in Y3.	27
Figure 12. srsRAN 4G Github star history in Y3,	27
Figure 13. Eclipse Zenoh's Github star history in the last three years.....	28
Figure 14. DAEMON booth at MWC 2023, with demos of the NI services developed by the project.	31
Figure 15. Natalia Romankevic (Net AI) presenting at the DAEMON first Industry workshop.	31
Figure 16. Miguel Camelo Botero (IMEC) chairing a session of the DAEMON-supported ANMS 2023.	32
Figure 17. DAEMON stand at the EuCNC 2023 conference.	32
Figure 18. DAEMON booth at the Industry Forum of the IEEE ICC 2023 conference.	33
Figure 19. DAEMON showcasing the Flowrest demo at IEEE NetSoft 2023, and the received award.	33
Figure 20. DAEMON supporting WiTar 2023.	34
Figure 21. Pictures from the session dedicated to the data challenge during the NetMob 2023 conference. Left: welcome message acknowledging the DAEMON project as a supporting initiative of the data challenge, and awarding of the winning contribution based on the dataset.....	34
Figure 22. Best Paper Awards at UMA premises in the DAEMON-supported ConfWS'23 workshop.....	35
Figure 23. Infocom World Conference 2023 website landing page.....	35
Figure 24. DAEMON booth at the Infocom World Conference 2023.....	35
Figure 25. The architectural framework proposed by the 5GPPP Arch WG [20].....	52
Figure 26. Mobile services whose traffic are present in the NetMob 2023 Data challenge dataset, ranked by the fraction of total demand they generate.	53

List of Tables

Table 1. Publications in scientific conferences (type C) and workshops (type W). Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.	16
Table 2. Publications in scientific journals. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project....	19
Table 3. Edited journals/books and organized events. Dates are in YY/MM format.....	22
Table 4. Books, Chapters, Whitepapers and Theses publications. Dates are in YY/MM format.	22
Table 5. Activities of DAEMON in the framework of 5G PPP and/or jointly with other projects.	23
Table 6. DAEMON SDO approved contributions during Y3.....	25
Table 7. DAEMON Open-source Contributions to external projects during Y3.....	27
Table 8. List of assets added to the DAEMON GitHub. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.	28
Table 9. Academic Activities during Y3.	29
Table 10. Key Industrial Exploitation Metrics.	30
Table 11. DAEMON patent applications during Y3.	30
Table 12. Overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation KPIs over the whole project.....	36
Table 13. List of publications in top-tier conferences during project lifetime. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.....	37
Table 14. List of publications in top-tier journals during project lifetime. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.....	39
Table 15. DAEMON SDO approved contributions since the start of the project to the end of Y3.	41
Table 16. DAEMON Innovations included in the Innovation Radar.	42
Table 17. Summary of the patents filed based on DAEMON solutions by the end of its execution.....	43
Table 18. Exploitation plan for vendors and service providers.	44
Table 19. Exploitation plan for network operators.	45
Table 20. Exploitation plan for small and medium enterprises.....	45
Table 21. Exploitation for academia and research centers.....	46
Table 22. Exploitation for vendors and SMEs.	50

List of Acronyms

3GPP	– Third Generation Partnership Project
5GPPP	– 5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	– 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AAAI	– Association for the Advancement of AI
AI	– Artificial Intelligence
AR	– Augmented Reality
B5G	– Beyond 5G
CoDEP	– Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan
CVD	– Coordinated Vulnerability Disclosure
DOC	– Digital Operations Center
DOI	– Digital Object Identifier System
DU	– Distributed Unit
eNB	– evolved Node B
ENI	– Experimental Networked Intelligence
ETSI	– European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FPGA	– Field Programmable Gate Array
gNB	– Next Generation NodeB
GSMA	– Groupe Speciale Mobile Association
IEEE	– Institute of Electronics and Electrical Engineering
IETF	– Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	– Internet of Things
IPR	– Intellectual Property Rights
IRTF	– Internet Research Task Force
ISG	– Industry Standards Group
ITU-T	– International Telecommunications Union – Telecommunications standardization sector
KPI	– Key Performance Indicator
L4S	– Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
MANO	– Management and orchestration
MEC	– Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	– Machine Learning
NFV	– Network Function Virtualization
NI	– Network Intelligence
NIS	– Network Information System
OEM	– Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPNFV	– Open Platform for NFV
ORAN	– Open Radio Access Network
O-RAN	– ORAN Alliance
PoC	– Proof of Concept
R&D	– Research and Development
RAN	– Radio Access Network
RF	– Radio Frequency
RFC	– Request for Comments
RIS	– Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
S1	– Interface that connects the RAN to the core
S1AP	– S1 Application Protocol
SDO	– Standard Development Organization
SDN	– Software Defined Networking
SM	– Standardization manager
SME	– Small and medium-sized enterprise
SCTP	– Stream Control Transmission Protocol
TSG	– Technical Specification Groups
UE	– User Equipment

V2X – Vehicle to Everything

VNF – Virtual Network Function

VR – Virtual Reality

vRAN – virtualized Radio Access Network

WG – Working Group

WP – Work Package

XR – Extended Reality

ZSM – Zero touch network and Service Management

Executive summary

The main contributions of this document are as follows.

- First, the deliverable presents of the main achievements during the third year of the project, and the during the three-month extension granted by the European Commission.
- Second, the deliverable presents of the exploitation plan to foster adoption of the project results beyond its conclusions.

DAEMON's CoDEP includes communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. **Communication** includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes explaining its research in layman's terms to the media and the public. **Dissemination** includes activities related to raising awareness of its results in a technical community working in the same research field. In general, this will be done through publications, participation, and the organization of technical events. Finally, **exploitation** (in accordance with the European IPR Helpdesk) covers activities aiming at using the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, such as developing, creating, and marketing products or processes, creating and providing a service, or standardization activities.

This deliverable covers the third (i.e. final) year of the DAEMON project plus an extension of three months (Y3), and thus focuses on the **final dissemination, demos, and proof-of-concepts (PoCs)** produced by the action. This is in line with the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan of the project. During Y3, dissemination and exploitation activities intensity peaked since the architecture and NI solutions have produced the desired research outcomes. Initial demonstrations of specific architecture concepts and NI solutions working in an integrated way were also provided during this phase. However, Y3 also focused on demonstrators and PoCs of the many solutions developed in the project, including activities involving multiple blocks of the architecture working in an integrated way.

Finally, with the end of the project, we enter the **long-lasting Impact** phase of the CoDEP, during which other research or exploitation actions shall take place beyond the action execution. This includes shaping the topics and framework of future research projects, exploiting DAEMON NI concepts in a market-oriented way by incorporating them into products and services, and leaving a footprint in standards through project contributions. The DAEMON CoDEP defines the various undertaken activities and defines related target metrics.

Below, we highlight the main outcomes of Year 3 and the three-month extension:

- Communication Activities:
 - Two press articles covering DAEMON have been released.
 - Five videos have been published.
 - Two webinars, two conferences and three workshops were organized.
 - Five DAEMON public deliverable and one DAEMON private deliverable were submitted.
 - The DAEMON website, its social media profiles (i.e., Twitter, Facebook, Facebook Page, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Youtube), and its data repositories (i.e., Zenodo, OpenAIRE and GitHub) have been continuously managed and updated.
- Disseminations Activities:
 - 27 scientific conference and workshop publications (including many top-ranked venues like ACM SIGCOMM, ACM MobiCom, ACM CoNEXT, IEEE INFOCOM or AAAI).
 - 22 JCR-indexed publications in scientific journals.
 - Continued participation of DAEMON representatives in many working groups of 5G PPP, with joint efforts with other 5G PPP projects leading to part of the output above.
- Exploitation Activities:
 - Eight new accepted contributions to SDOs.
 - Three new contributions to open-source projects.
 - Six new demonstrators developed by the project and showcased at major events.

1 Introduction

The Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Final Report of DAEMON covers the three types of activities during the final year of DAEMON and its three-month extension.

Figure 1 shows the various phases of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities of the project from Y1 to Y3 and beyond the end of the project, as we initially planned it from D6.1 [1]. During Y3, the project was in the **Demos and PoCs** phase. This document therefore outlines the activities that the DAEMON consortium carried out during this time, while also laying forth a plan for ensuring the realization of the **Long-lasting impact** phase after the project conclusion.

For the sake of completeness, we recall that during year 1, the project was in the “Raise Awareness” phase (M0 to M11), and the results of this are clearly laid out in D6.1 [2]. During year 2, the project was in the “Presentation of results” phase (M12 to M23), and the results of this are clearly laid out in D6.2 [3].

Figure 1. DAEMON Dissemination & Exploitation Plan.

During year 3 plus the three-month extension – the **Demos and PoCs** phase – the project increased its focus on developing demonstration and proof-of-concept (PoC) prototypes of designed NI-aided systems. These activities helped validate the NI mechanisms derived in WP3, WP4 and WP5 and, in the context of WP6, helped disseminate and communicate the project results to the scientific community and the general public. This phase resulted in reaching the peak of research papers being published outlining the final research outcomes. Most of the analytical results gathered via production were also analyzed during this stage and disseminated at top-tier scientific conferences and workshops, including a number of live demonstrations of the solutions developed in the project by DAEMON representatives at events such as Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2023, EuCNC 2023 or IEEE ICC 2023, among others.

Efforts towards contributing to open-source projects and SDOs also peaked during this phase of the project. Multiple solutions from different partners were integrated into Zenoh, Zenoh-flow, and srsRAN, wrapping-up the open-source contributions for the first two years of the project. Our increased effort to contribute to SDOs led to 8 new contributions to O-RAN, bringing the total number of contributions to the standardization efforts of various bodies, including ETSI-RIS, 3GPP, O-RAN, to a total of 45.

Exploitation activities during this time led to the successful filing of two additional patents (bringing up the total number of filed patents to nine during the duration of the project), in addition to the publication of new datasets and codes associated to the DAEMON activities as open source, and academic activities like research visits during Y3.

Over the course of Y3 and the three-month extension, the consortium focused strongly on the following aspects in line with the DAEMON CoDEP.

- Dissemination
 - Continued publication of the project research results in highly reputed and selective scientific conferences, workshops and journals.
 - Defense of PhD and Master theses on the topics of the project.
 - Participation in public exhibitions and live demonstrations of proof-of-concepts and integrated solutions.
 - Organization of special events, including technical workshops.
 - Collaboration with other projects.

- Exploitation
 - Developing demonstrators of the DAEMON solutions, showcasing the advantages of the NI services designed by the project in practical settings.
 - Implementing pilots deploying specific NI services developed in DAEMON in production-grade environments.
 - Filing patents to protect the solutions of the project for future commercialization.
 - Ensuring full and open accessibility to the majority of the software and datasets produced by DAEMON during its execution.
 - Contributing to standardization bodies.

After the end of the action – during the **Long-lasting impact** phase of the CoDEP – partners of DAEMON will keep disseminating the results of the project and exploiting the NI services designed and developed during DAEMON towards impacting the product or service portfolio of the vendors in the consortium or through enforcing IPR and licenses. In particular, the three months extension was instrumental to be able to complete two pilots for DAEMON activities, thus reaching a higher TRL (TRL 5) for those activities than initially planned and ensuring a much higher visibility and credibility of the associated NI services towards their future exploitation in full-fledged mobile network infrastructures.

In the rest of this document, we present the major achievements during the last stage of the project, as well as extra communication, dissemination and exploitation activities after the project officially ends.

We summarize the main achievements from Y3 as follows.

- Communication Activities
 - Two press articles delivered.
 - Nine oral communications provided.
 - Seven videos published.
 - Ten photos of DAEMON-supported events published.
 - Two webinars organized.
 - Three conferences and one academic workshop organized.
 - Two industrial workshops organized.
 - Seven DAEMON public deliverables and two private deliverables were submitted.
 - Over 500 social network posts published.
 - 5,995 new visits to the DAEMON website.
 - 70 views and 50 downloads on average for each individual DAEMON asset.
- Disseminations Activities
 - 27 scientific conference and workshop publications (including many top-ranked venues like ACM MobiCom, ACM CoNEXT, IEEE INFOCOM or AAAI).
 - 22 JCR-indexed publications in scientific journals.
 - Continued participation of DAEMON representatives in many working groups of 5G PPP, with joint efforts with other 5G PPP projects leading to part of the output above.
- Exploitation Activities
 - Two pilots executed, reaching TRL5 for two activities, one of which was already included among the five DAEMON products accepted in the Innovation Radar during Y2.
 - Eight new accepted contributions to SDOs
 - Three contributions to large open-source projects.
 - Six new demonstrators developed by the project and showcased at major events.
 - Seven new open-source software assets added to DAEMON's GitHub.

2 Achievements in year 3

In this section, we summarize the achievements of the project during Y3 and the three-month extension and concerning the communication and dissemination activities, patents, industrial events, contributions to SDOs. For previous years achievements, we kindly refer the reader to D6.2 [2] and D6.3 [3].

2.1 Communication activities

2.1.1 News and press releases

We released two press article covering DAEMON. Specifically:

1. (21/07/2023) DAEMON: Natively integrating Network Intelligence in 6G mobile networks by Marco Fiore (IMDEA): <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/daemon-natively-integrating-network-intelligence-in-6g-mobile-networks/35081/>
2. (02/11/2023) Demonstrating native AI for mobile network operation by Marco Fiore (IMDEA): <https://www.innovationnewsnetwork.com/demonstrating-native-ai-for-mobile-network-operation/39129/>.

We performed nine oral communications related to DAEMON:

1. (06/06/2023) The 6G workshop series by Andres Garcia-Saavedra (NEC) at Hexa-X: <https://hexa-x.eu/eucnc-6g-summit-2023-the-6g-workshop-series-by-hexa-x/>
2. (23/05/2023) Self-organizing, self-managing (ai-driven) autonomous 6g networks by Miguel Camelo (IMEC) at ICC 2023 Industry Program: <https://icc2023.ieee-icc.org/program/industry-program/industry-presentations>
3. (13/12/2023) ANCHOR: Una solución de IA para la detección proactiva de anomalías en la conectividad de dispositivos IoT by Andra Lutu (TID) at TEFCon 2023.
4. (29/05/2023) Novel Scenarios for the Wireless Internet of Things by Andra Lutu (TID) at Dagstuhl Seminar 23222: <https://www.dagstuhl.de/23222>
5. (21/05/2023) Deep Dive into Interconnection in the Mobile Ecosystem by Andra Lutu (TID) at PAM Keynote: <https://pam2023.networks.imdea.org/keynote/>
6. (10/06/2023) Cost and energy-efficient RAN virtualization by Andres Garcia-Saavedra (NEC) at ACM MobiArch 2023 Keynote: <https://mobiarch2023.github.io/program.html>
7. (01/04/2023) Deep Dive into Interconnection in the Mobile Ecosystem by Andra Lutu (TID) at Open Networks and Services Whitepaper: <https://h2020daemon.eu/industry-workshop-2023/>
8. (01/11/2023) Conference invited Talk "Hacia una red 5G/6G con inteligencia nativa: Oportunidades e integración en los nuevos desarrollos de redes móviles" by Antonio Bazco Noguera (IMDEA) at III Jornada 5G - Univ. Oviedo.
9. (01/10/2023) Conference invited Talk "Natively integrating AI in mobile networks" by Marco Fiore (IMDEA) at IEEE 9th World Forum on Internet of Things (IEEE WF-IoT).

We published seven videos:

1. (27/03/2023) Opening session + Award announcements at PAM by Anna Brunström, Marcel Flores and Marco Fiore (IMDEA): https://youtu.be/Ld_BGNj3_9Q
2. (27/09/2023) Thesis Post-Defense: Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach by Daniel-Jesus Munoz (UMA) at Ulm University: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10009876>
3. (01/02/2023) Flowrest demo by IMDEA at MWC, INFOCOM and NetSoft: <https://youtu.be/3bY4vDdhcQQ>
4. (03/06/2023) NIP user plane demo by IMEC, WINGS and ZETTASCALE at European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC) 2023: <https://youtu.be/-7qOyYUBKf0>
5. (22/01/2024) ITAREA optimal deployment demo by Lidia Fuentes (UMA) at the International Conference on Service-Oriented Computing: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10419873>
6. (22/12/2023) SAVRUS: The Smart Analyser of Variability Requirements in Unknown Spaces demo by Daniel-Jesus Munoz (UMA) at Jornadas de la Sociedad de Ingeniería de Software y Tecnologías de Desarrollo de Software 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10595123>
7. (22/01/2024) Edge Cloud Simulator demo by Lidia Fuentes (UMA) at the 2022 IEEE/ACM 15th International Conference on Utility and Cloud Computing (UCC): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10601527>.

We contributed to two webinars:

1. (19/01/2023) DAEMON: Machine learning-based resource orchestration in beyond-5G networks by D. De Vleeschauwer (NBL) at ICT-52 Workshop on 6G: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g-2023/>
2. (19/01/2023) DAEMON: A network intelligence plane for 6G networks by M. Gramaglia (UC3M) at ICT-52 Workshop on 6G: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g-2023/>.

We organized three academic conferences and one academic workshop:

1. The 19th Passive and Active Measurement Conference by Marco Fiore (IMDEA): <https://pam2023.networks.imdea.org/>
2. 25th International Workshop on Configuration (ConfWS 2023) by José Miguel Horcas, José Ángel Galindo, Richard Comptoi-Taupe and Lidia Fuentes (UMA): <https://confws.github.io/2023/>
3. 27th ACM International Systems and Software Product Line Conference - Demonstrations and Tool Track co-chair by Mónica Pinto (UMA): <https://2023.splc.net/>
4. 28th ACM International Systems and Software Product Line Conference - Research Track co-chair by Mónica Pinto (UMA): <https://2024.splc.net/>.

We organized two industry workshops:

1. DAEMON organized the "DAEMON 1st industry workshop": <https://h2020daemon.eu/industry-workshop-2023/>
2. DAEMON co-organized its 2nd industry workshop entitled "Exploring the Intersection of 6G and Artificial Intelligence: Unleashing the Potential of Next-Gen Technologies" at EuCNC 2023: <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-5/>.

We supported two actions:

1. IMDEA supported the NetMob 2023 Data Challenge: <https://netmob2023challenge.networks.imdea.org/>
2. NEC supported the RAN Subdomain in the "Open Networks and Services" whitepaper.

We have also produced seven public DAEMON deliverables and two private DAEMON deliverable:

1. D1.3 "Year 2 Management Report" on February 28th, 2023 (*Private*)
2. D2.3 "Final DAEMON Network Intelligence framework and toolsets" on June 28th, 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8271463>
3. D3.3 "Final design of real-time control and VNF intelligence mechanisms" on September 30th, 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10560148>
4. D4.3 "Final design of intelligent orchestration and management mechanisms" on September 30th, 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10654549>
5. D5.2 "Report on Evaluation Results and Initial Proof-of-Concept Demonstrations" on March 31st, 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7818319>
6. D6.3 "Report on Communication, dissemination and exploitation results and updated CoDEP for Y3" on January 31st, 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7594492>
7. D5.3 "Final evaluation results and proof-of-concept demonstrations" on March 31st, 2024 (DOI pending).
8. D6.4 "Final report on communication, dissemination and exploitation, and exploitation plan for after the project" on March 31st, 2024 (DOI pending).
9. D1.4 "Year 3 Management Report" on March 31st, 2024 (*Private*).

2.1.2 Web, social media and project communication material

The DAEMON's official website was continuously updated with information about all project activities and results, at the following URL: <https://h2020daemon.eu/>. We show the Deliverables page in Figure 2.

The consortium is also collecting visibility metrics based on many analytic services: as an example, Figure 3 displays the Advanced Page Visit Counter. We have a total of 59,164 visits, 24,764 of which in 2023 alone, and 1,900 since from February 2024. Additionally, the landing page has been the most visited, with approximately 23 unique loads a day.

We provide the results of the most visited pages from Google Analytics in Figure 4. We note that from the 24,764 loads only in 2023, 5,995 were unique website visits, of which 1,542 were of totally different Ips subnets. Compared to Y1, we doubled these numbers, and increased by 15% compared to Y2. Again, Home, followed by the ANMS' 23 workshop page, and the Industry Workshop page had the most traffic.

Figure 2. DAEMON Deliverable page on project website.

Figure 3. Total DAEMON website visits.

Page title and screen class	Views	Users	Views per user	Average engagement time
	5,995 100% of total	1,542 100% of total	3.72 Avg 0%	58s Avg 0%
1 Home - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	2,747	993	2.77	23s
2 ANMS'23 - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	866	277	3.13	59s
3 Industry Workshop 2023 - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	483	142	3.40	47s
4 Publications - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	386	119	3.24	47s
5 Deliverables - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	379	122	3.11	35s
6 About - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	234	95	2.46	27s
7 Consortium - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	234	94	2.49	28s
8 Contact Us - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	228	93	2.45	14s
9 Overview - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sEIf-Learning MOBILE Networks	189	80	2.36	27s

Figure 4. Google Analytics Report of most visited pages.

Further, we explain the results we include in Figure 5, reporting the type of devices used to access the DAEMON website: our followers tend to access through Desktop or Laptop devices mostly, and only occasionally through mobile devices or through tablets. Compared to Y1 and Y2, the access with Tablets decreased, which is expected with their decreased popularity.

Based on the results of Figure 6, we note that visitors mostly use Chrome web explorer, followed at a distance by Safari, Edge and Firefox. Compared to Y2, accessing through Edge has increased and Firefox decreased.

The last statistics we report are demographics from Google Analytics, in Figure 7. The two most influential countries besides those in the European Union are, as expected, United States of America and China. Spanish audience was also expected as some communications are in Spanish venues. Compared to Y2, visits were more distributed among many more countries, which is a positive signal of wider outreach.

Figure 5. Google Analytics Report of devices used to access DAEMON site.

Figure 6. Google Analytics Report of web-browsers used to access DAEMON site.

Figure 7. Google Analytics Report of DAEMON site demographics.

The consortium also maintained the different DAEMON social network profiles, as follows.

1. Twitter: <https://twitter.com/h2020daemon>
2. Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemon>
3. Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemoneu/>
4. Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/h2020daemon/>
5. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/daemon-daemon-717591202/>
6. Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbccd2DulaSMX_69uaLZy7A
7. Github: <https://github.com/h2020daemon>.

All these accounts are also made available on the DAEMON official webpage. Social networks feeds are displayed in real-time throughout the landing page. Compared to previous years, Twitter Feeds by were replanced by Facebook Feeds after Twitter’s rebranding to X; the reason is that the new API of X Feeds is a paid-by-print price plan, while Facebook Feed API is free up to a reasonable usage.

A total of 500 meaningful posts have been shared (100 per social network, besides the ones on YouTube). In X, we have reached the best numbers; a total of 18,342 impressions, which represents a ~65% increase compared to Year 1 and a ~15% increase compared to Year 2. We show in Figure 8 an example of these analytics.

Figure 8. Twitter Analytics Report of tweets impressions and engagement of the last three months.

On average, we slightly increased the engagement ratio compared to Y2. Figure 9 shows the Twitter profile of DAEMON, which shows that 77 accounts are subscribed to our news, which represents only a small increase compared to Y2. This is expected as the marketshare of X decreased.

Figure 9. Official Profile of DAEMON on Twitter.

The rest of the social networks show similar analytics.

2.2 Dissemination activities

In this section, we detail the dissemination activities of the project just for the third year and three-month extension (Y3). DAEMON peaked with multiple dissemination activities as the main components of DAEMON have had finished. This includes research and demo presentations in multiple conferences, seminars and forums. At the end, we also provide a summary with respect to the KPIs considering the complete length of DAEMON; for a detailed information of Y1 and Y2, we kindly refer the readers to Deliverables 6.2 [2] and 6.3 [3], respectively.

2.2.1 Publications and technical dissemination

The following tables present DAEMON peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals and studies, demos, and posters in scientific conferences. In the first column of each table, we also specify the corresponding tasks that are related to these publications. The rows in each table are ordered by publication date from the oldest to the newest.

Table 1 presents 27 publications in scientific conferences (C) and workshops (W) at top-tier venues like IEEE INFOCOM, ACM SIGMETRICS, AAI and ACM MobiCom. Table 2 presents 25 publications in top-tier scientific journals, like Elsevier’s Knowledge Based Systems, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications, and IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking. We also

remark that many of such top-quality contributions stem from multiparty collaborative work within the DAEMON consortium. Among them, we highlight the work “Orchestration Procedures for the Network Intelligence Stratum in 6G Networks” between most of the partners in the consortium.

Besides these specific collaboration, project wide contributions have been disseminated also through scientific papers like the ones published at CCNC 2023 and EuCNC 2023.

Table 1. Publications in scientific conferences (type C) and workshops (type W). Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.

Date Tasks	Type	Title	Event	Authors	Related WP or activity	Open Access DOI
23/01 T3.4 T5.2	C	Flowrest: Practical Flow-Level Inference in Programmable Switches with Random Forests	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A.T.-J. Akem, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550150
23/01 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	C	AutoManager: a Meta-Learning Model for Network Management from Intertwined Forecasts	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A. Collet, A. Bazco Nogueras, A. Banchs, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A32, A33	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550176
23/01 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	C	Spotting Deep Neural Network Vulnerabilities in Mobile Traffic Forecasting with an Explainable AI Lens	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	S. Moghadas, C. Fiandrino, A. Collet, G. Attanasio, M. Fiore, J. Widmer (IMDEA)	A25	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550186
22/12 T2.1 T2.2 T2.3 T2.4	W	DAEMON: A Network Intelligence Plane for 6G Networks	2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops	Camelo, Miguel; Gramaglia, Marco; Soto, Paola; Fuentes, Lidia; Ballesteros, Joaquín; Bazco-Nogueras, Antonio; Garcia-Aviles, Gines; Latré, Steven; Garcia-Saavedra, Andres; Fiore, Marco (IMEC, UC3M, UMA, IMDEA, I2CAT, NEC)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7555198
23/05 T3.1 T5.2	C	Spotlight on 5G: Performance, Device Evolution and Challenges from a Mobile Operator Perspective	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	P. Parastar, A. Lutu, O. Alay, G. Caso, D. Perino (TID)	A13	https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOCOM53939.2023.10229108
21/11 T4.4	W	A Machine Learning Approach for Service Function Chain Embedding in Cloud Datacenter Networks	IEEE CLOUDNET 2023	Tom Wassing, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Chrysa Papagianni (NBL)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8170927
23/06 T3.4 T5.2	C	Showcasing In-Switch Machine Learning Inference	IEEE NetSoft 2023	A.T.-J. Akem, B. Bütün, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125040
23/06 T4.4	C	Orchestration Procedures for the Network Intelligence Stratum in 6G Networks	EuCNC 2023	Varied authors (IMDEA, UC3M, IMEC, NEC, WINGS, TUD, UMA, TID, ZSCALE)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8120773

23/06 T3.4 T5.2	C	Fast Detection of Cyberattacks on the Metaverse through User-plane Inference	MetaCom 2023	B. Bütün ,A.T.-J. Akem, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8125021
23/03 T4.2	C	Reservation of Virtualized Resources with Optimistic Online Learning	IEEE ICC 2023	Jean Baptiste Monteil; George Iosifidis; Ivana Dusparic (TUD)	A14	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134360
23/06 T2.3 T2.4 T3.2	W	Predicting network performance using GNNs: generalization to larger unseen networks	IEEE/IFIP NOMS 2022	Miquel Ferreras, Paola Soto, Migue Camelo, Luis Fabregas, Pere Vilà (IMEC)	A16	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7684179
23/09 T3.2	C	FLAMA: A collaborative effort to build a new framework for the automated analysis of feature models	ACM SPLC 2023	José A. Galindo, Jose-Miguel Horcas, Alexander Felfering, David Fernandez-Amoros, David Benavides (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022408
23/09 T3.2	C	Belief-Driven Software Product Line Development and Evolution	ACM SPLC 2023	Lola Burgueño, Jose-Miguel Horcas, Jörg Kienzle (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022601
23/09 T3.2	C	Elimination of constraints for parallel analysis of feature models	ACM SPLC 2023	J.-M. Horcas, J. Ballesteros, M. Pinto, L. Fuentes (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10022639
23/10 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	C	kaNSaaS: Combining Deep Learning and Optimization for Practical Overbooking of Network Slices	ACM MobiHoc 2023	Sergi Alcalá-Marín, Antonio Bazco-Nogueras, Albert Banchs, Marco Fiore (IMDEA)	A31	https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10017773
23/10 T2.2 T2.4	C	A Data Flow Programming Framework for 6G-Enabled Internet of Things Applications.	IEEE WF-IoT 2023	Baldoni, G., Loudet, J., Guimarães, C., Nair, S., Corsaro, A. (ZSCALE)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10025848
TBC T2.2 T2.4	C	Resource Allocation of Multi-user Workloads in Cloud and Edge Data-Centers Using Reinforcement Learning	IEEE CNSM 2023	Julian Jimenez, Paola Soto, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Chia-Yu Chang, Yorick De Bock, Steven Latré, Miguel Camelo (IMEC, NBL)	A16	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10007880
23/12 T3.3	C	Data-driven Analysis of the Cost-Performance Trade-off of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in a Production Network	ACM CoNEXT 2023	M. Rossanese, A. Garcia-Saavedra, A. Lutu, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, TID)	A23	https://doi.org/10.1145/3629134
24/05 T3 T1	C	Mean-Field Multi-Agent Contextual Bandit for Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation in vRANs	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Lo-Schiavo, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, IMDEA, i2CAT)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686512

24/05 T3 T1	C	OREO: O-RAN intelligence Orchestration of xApp-based network services	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	F. Mungari, C. Puligheddu, A. Garcia-Saavedra, C. F. Chiasserini (NEC)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686449
24/05 T3 T1	C	YinYangRAN: Resource Multiplexing in GPU-Accelerated Virtualized RANs	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	L. Lo Schiavo, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Fiore, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, IMDEA, i2CAT)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686545
24/05 T3 T1	C	ORANUS: Latency-tailored Orchestration via Stochastic Network Calculus in 6G O-RAN	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	O. Adamuz-Hinojosa, L. Zanzi, V. Sciancalepore, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, i2CAT)	A5	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.03812
24/05 T3 T1	C	Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits	AAAI 2024	J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	WP2 – Task 2.4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686581
24/09 T3 T1	C	CloudRIC: Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Virtualization with Shared Heterogeneous Computing	ACM MobiCom 2024	L. Lo Schiavo, G. Garcia-Aviles, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, i2CAT, IMDEA, UC3M)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693534
24/06 T4.1 T4.2	C	Fair Resource Allocation in Virtualized O-RAN Platforms	ACM SIGMETRICS 2024	F. Aslan, G. Iosifidis, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, TUD)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686646
24/05 T3.4 T5.2	C	Jewel: Resource-Efficient Joint Packet and Flow Level Inference in Programmable Switches	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	A.T.-J. Akem, B. Bütün, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731523
24/02 T3.2	W	Variability in data transformation: towards data migration product lines	VaMoS 2024	David Romero Organvidez, David Benavides José Miguel Horcas, María Teresa Gómez López (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10715954

Two presentations were also uploaded to the DAEMON Zenodo community as a complement to these publications above. The presentations are:

1. (22/09/2023) "Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach" by Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto and Lidia Fuentes (UMA) presented at UMA and the University of Ulm: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019392>.
2. (09/04/2023) "Detecting Feature Influences to Quality Attributes in Large and Partially Measured Spaces using Smart Sampling and Dynamic Learning in Knowledge-Based Systems" by Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto and Lidia Fuentes (UMA) presented at Jornadas de Ingeniería del Software y Bases de Datos (JISBD) 2023: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019456>.

Table 2. Publications in scientific journals. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.

Date Tasks	Title	Journal	Authors	Related WP or activity	Open Access DOI
23/10 T3.2 T4.1	HADES: An NFV solution for energy-efficient placement and resource allocation in heterogeneous infrastructures	Journal of Network and Computer Applications	Angel Cañete, Mercedes Amor and Lidia Fuentes (UMA)	A7	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7712024
23/04 T3.2	Detecting Feature Influences to Quality Attributes in Large and Partially Measured Spaces using Smart Sampling and Dynamic Learning in Knowledge-Based Systems	Knowledge Based Systems Journal	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.knosys.2023.110558 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019456
23/06 T2.2 T4.4	Network Intelligence for NFV scaling in closed-loop architectures	IEEE Communications Magazine	Paola Soto, Miguel Camelo, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Yorick De Bock, Chia-Yu Chang, Juan F. Botero, Steven Latré (IMEC, NOKIA)	A16	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705141
23/10 T2.2	O-RAN: Analysis of Latency-critical Interfaces and Overview of Time Sensitive Networking Solutions	IEEE Communications Standards Magazine	Esteban Municio, Gines Garcia-Aviles, Andres Garcia-Saavedra and Xavier Costa-Pérez (i2CAT, NEC)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021416
23/04 T4.4	Deep Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning with Minimal Cross-Agent Communication for SFC Partitioning	IEEE Access	Angelos Pentelas, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Chia-Yu Chang, Koen De Schepper, Panagiotis Papadimitriou (NBL)	A30	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3269576
23/04 T4.1	EdgeBOL: A Bayesian Learning Approach for the Joint Orchestration of vRANs and Mobile Edge AI	IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking	Jose A. Ayala-Romero; Andres Garcia-Saavedra; Xavier Costa-Pérez; George Iosifidis (NEC, TUD)	A5	https://doi.org/10.1109/TNET.2023.3268981
23/09 T2.2 T2.4	Digital Twins for Next-Generation Mobile Networks: Applications and Solutions	IEEE Communications Magazine	N. Apostolakis; L. Chatzieftheriou ; D. Bega; M. Gramaglia; A. Banchs (UC3M, IMDEA)	A29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913097

23/01 T2.4	A Methodology to Design Quantized Deep Neural Networks for Automatic Modulation Recognition	Algorithms	David Góez, Paola Soto, Steven Latré, Natalia Gaviria, Miguel Camelo (IMEC)	WP2 – Task2.4	https://doi.org/10.3390/a15120441
23/01 T4.4	Quid pro Quo in Streaming Services: Algorithms for Cooperative Recommendations	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	Dimitra Tsigkari; George Iosifidis; Akis Spyropoulos (TU Delft)	A27	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134257
23/01 T4.2	Lazy Lagrangians for Optimistic Learning With Budget Constraints	IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking	Daron Anderson; George Iosifidis; Douglas J. Leith (TU Delft)	WP2 – Task2.4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134298
23/03 T3.2	A modular metamodel and refactoring rules to achieve software product line interoperability	The Journal of Systems & Software	Jose-Miguel Horcas, Mónica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2022.111579
23/05 T3.2	Transforming Numerical Feature Models into Propositional Formulas and the Universal Variability Language	Journal of Systems and Software	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes, Don Batory (UMA)	A6	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2023.111770
23/07 T2.3 T2.4 T3.2	Improving network delay predictions using GNNs	Journal of Networks and Systems Management	Miquel Farreras, Paola Soto, Miguel Camelo, Lluís Fabregas, Pere Vilà (IMEC)	A12	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8139780
23/09 T3.1	Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) Experimentation Platform: Design and Datasets	IEEE Communications Magazine	J. Xavier-Salvat, J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Zanzi, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021480
23/09 T2.2 T2.4	Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network	IEEE Communications Magazine	Gabriele Baldoni, Jose Quevedo, Carlos Guimaraes, Antonio de la Oliva, Angelo Corsaro (ZSCALE)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8335532
23/09 T2.2 T2.4	A Dataflow-Oriented Approach for Machine-Learning-Powered Internet of Things Applications	Electronics Magazine 2023, 12, 3940	Baldoni, G., Teixeira, R., Guimarães, C., Antunes, M., Gomes, D. and Corsaro, A. (ZSCALE)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10026073
23/10 T2.4	Network Automation and Data Analytics in 3GPP 5G Systems	IEEE Network	M Garcia-Martin, M. Gramaglia, P. Serrano (UC3M)	WP2 – Task 2.1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8422077

23/10 T2.2 T3.3	AI-Empowered Management and Orchestration of Vehicular Systems in the Beyond 5G Era	IEEE Network	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac, Miguel Camelo, Chia-Yu Chang, Paola Soto, Luca Cominardi, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Steven Latré, Johann M. Marquez-Barja (IMEC, NBL, ZSCALE)	A30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082536
23/11 T3 T1	ATHENA: Machine Learning and Reasoning for Radio Resources Scheduling in vRAN systems	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications	Apostolakis, N., Gramaglia, M., Chatzieftheriou, L. E., Subramanya, T., Banchs, A., & Sanneck, H. (UC3M, IMDEA)	A29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10183985
23/12 T4.3	AIRIC: Orchestration of Virtualized Radio Access Networks with Noisy Neighbours	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications	J. Xavier Salvat, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Li, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	A24	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10353739
23/12 T2.2	Designing the Network Intelligence Stratum for 6G Networks	Computer Networks {under review}	P. Soto, M. Camelo, G. Garcia-Aviles, E. Municio, M. Gramaglia, E. Kosmatos, N. Slamnik-Krijestorac, D. De Vleeschauwer, A. Bazco-Nogueras, L. Fuentes, J. Ballesteros, A. Lutu, L. Cominardi, I. Paez, S. Alcalá-Marin, L. E. Chatzieftheriou, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Fiore (IMEC, i2CAT, UC3M, WINGS, NOKIA, IMDEA, UMA, TID, ZSCALE, NEC)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10619439
23/03 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	Explainable and Transferable Loss Meta-Learning for Zero-Touch Anticipatory Network Management	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	A. Collet, A. Bazco-Nogueras, A. Banchs, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A32	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10821655

Additionally, the DAEMON consortium edited 1 journal special issue and participated in the organization of several top academic conferences and workshops, as listed in Table 3.

Table 3. Edited journals/books and organized events. Dates are in YY/MM format.

Date	Type	Event or journal	Authors	URL
23/05	Workshop organization	ANMS – 2nd International Workshop on Autonomous Network Management in 5G and Beyond Systems (ANSM 2022) at IEEE NOMS 2023	Miguel Camelo, Francesc Wilhelmi, Paul Harvey (IMEC)	https://h2020daemon.eu/workshop-anms-2023/
23/03	Conference organization	The 19th Passive and Active Measurement Conference (PAM 2023)	Marco Fiore (IMDEA)	https://pam2023.net/works.imdea.org/
23/09	Workshop organization	25th International Workshop on Configuration (ConfWS 2023)	José Miguel Horcas, José Ángel Galindo, Richard Comptoi-Taupe, Lidia Fuentes (UMA)	https://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3509/
23/10	Special Issue editing	Special Issue "Tools and Software at the Systems and Software Product Line Conference (SPLC 2022)" of the Science of Computer Programming Journal	Mónica Pinto (UMA)	https://2022.splc.net/
23/09	Conference organization	Proceedings of the 27 th ACM International Systems and Software Product Line Conference – Volume B (SPLC 2023)	Paolo Arcaini, Maurice H. ter Beek, Gilles Perrouin, Iris Reinhartz-Berger, Ivan Machado, Silvia Regina Vergilio, Rick Rabiser, Tao Yue, Xavier Devroey, Mónica Pinto, Hironori Washizaki (UMA)	https://2023.splc.net/

The DAEMON project published 1 whitepaper, 1 book, 1 book chapter and 2 PhD Theses, as in Table 4.

Table 4. Books, Chapters, Whitepapers and Theses publications. Dates are in YY/MM format.

Date Tasks	Title	Publisher	Author	Open Access DOI
23/06 T1 T2	5G PPP / 5G IA	The European 5G Annual Journal 2023	Marco Fiore (IMDEA)	https://5g-ppp.eu/annual-journal/
23/09 T3.2	UMA PhD. Thesis "Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach"	Repositorio Institucional de la Universidad de Málaga	Daniel-Jesus Munoz (UMA)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10007921 Slides: https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10019392
24/06 T2.4	Book "Towards Sustainable and Trustworthy 6G: Challenges, Enablers,	Boston-Delft: now publishers,	Ömer Bulakçı, Xi Li, Marco Gramaglia, Anastasius	http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/9781638282396

	and Architectural Design”		Gavras, Mikko Uusitalo, Patrik Rugeland , Mauro Boldi (UC3M, NEC)	
24/06 T3	Chapter “Towards Natively Intelligent Networks”	Boston-Delft: now publishers,	Marco Gramaglia, Xi Li, Ginés García-Aviles, et al. (UC3M, NEC, I2CAT, IMDEA)	http://dx.doi.org/10.1561/9781638282396.ch5
24/18 T3.2 T4.1	UMA PhD. Thesis “Energy-efficient tasks assignment for heterogeneous deployment architectures on Edge Computing”	Repositorio Institucional de la Universidad de Málaga	Angel Cañete (UMA)	NA

Finally, in Figure 10 we show an example of the analytics for DAEMON publications. In general, each asset uploaded for at least 3 months has a minimum of 70 views and 50 downloads. While the number of views decreased with respect to Y2, the number of downloads (engagement) increased, including cases with more downloads than views.

Figure 10. Example of the Zenodo analytics for each published asset in the DAEMON community.

2.2.2 Synergies with other projects

The DAEMON project carried out several collaborative activities with other projects funded under 5G PPP calls towards a coordinated action inside the 5G-PPP during its second year. In addition, the project also generated synergies with projects funded by the new SNS-JU calls of the Horizon Europe framework programme that started in 2022. Such activities are summarized in Table 5 below and include 15 joint research and publication of scientific results, participation in 5G PPP boards and Working Groups (WG), and contributions to one white paper and one book.

Table 5. Activities of DAEMON in the framework of 5G PPP and/or jointly with other projects.

Item	Explanation
Joint paper	Joint scientific publication with the H2020 project “RISE-6G – Reconfigurable Intelligent Sustainable Environments for 6G Wireless Networks (101017011)”, titled “Data-driven Analysis of the Cost-Performance Trade-off of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in a Production Network” at ACM CoNEXT 2023

Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU projects "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)" and "ORIGAMI – Optimized Resource Integration and Global Architecture for Mobile Infrastructure for 6G (101139270)", titled "Mean-Field Multi-Agent Contextual Bandit for Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation in vRANs" at IEEE INFOCOM 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU projects "PREDICT-6G – PRogrammable AI-Enabled Deterministic neTworking for 6G (101095890)" and "CENTRIC – Towards an AI-native, user-centric air interface for 6G networks (101096379)", titled "OREO: O-RAN intelligence Orchestration of xApp-based network services" at IEEE INFOCOM 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU projects "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)" and "ORIGAMI – Optimized Resource Integration and Global Architecture for Mobile Infrastructure for 6G (101139270)", titled "YinYangRAN: Resource Multiplexing in GPU-Accelerated Virtualized RANs" at IEEE INFOCOM 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "ORIGAMI – Optimized Resource Integration and Global Architecture for Mobile Infrastructure for 6G (101139270)", titled "Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits" at AAAI 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "ORIGAMI – Optimized Resource Integration and Global Architecture for Mobile Infrastructure for 6G (101139270)", titled "CloudRIC: Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Virtualization with Shared Heterogeneous Computing" at ACM MobiCom 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU projects "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)" and "ORIGAMI – Optimized Resource Integration and Global Architecture for Mobile Infrastructure for 6G (101139270)", titled "Fair Resource Allocation in Virtualized O-RAN Platforms" at ACM SIGMETRICS 2024
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)", titled "O-RAN: Analysis of Latency-critical Interfaces and Overview of Time Sensitive Networking Solutions" at IEEE Communications Standards Magazine
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)", titled "EdgeBOL: A Bayesian Learning Approach for the Joint Orchestration of vRANs and Mobile Edge AI" at IEEE Transactions on Networking
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "TrialsNet – TRials Supported By Smart Networks Beyond 5G (101095871)", titled "Digital Twins for Next-Generation Mobile Networks: Applications and Solutions" at IEEE Communications Magazine
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)", titled "Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) Experimentation Platform: Design and Datasets" at IEEE Communications Magazine
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "Hexa-X-II – A holistic flagship towards the 6G network platform and system (101095759)", titled "Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network" at IEEE Communications Magazine
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "TrialsNet – TRials Supported By Smart Networks Beyond 5G (101095871)", titled "Network Automation and Data Analytics in 3GPP 5G Systems" at IEEE Network
Joint paper	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "TrialsNet – TRials Supported By Smart Networks Beyond 5G (101095871)", titled "ATHENA: Machine Learning and Reasoning for Radio Resources Scheduling in vRAN systems" at IEEE Journal on Selected Areas of Communications

	Joint scientific paper with the SNS-JU project "BeGREEN – Beyond 5G Artificial Intelligence Assisted Energy Efficient Open Radio Access Network (101097083)", titled "AIRIC: Orchestration of Virtualized Radio Access Networks with Noisy Neighbours" at IEEE Journal on Selected Areas of Communications
5G PPP board	Participation in Steering Board (M. Fiore – IMDEA)
5G PPP board	Participation in Technical Board (A. Garcia-Saavedra – NEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in 5G Architecture WG (Xi Li – NEC, M. Gramaglia – UC3M, M. Camelo – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Vision and Societal Challenges WG (M. Fiore – IMDEA)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Software Networks WG (C.-Y. Chang – NOKIA, J. Marquez-Barja – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in 5G Automotive WG (J. Marquez-Barja – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation WG (A. Garcia-Saavedra – NEC, V. Kosmatos – WINGS)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Pre-Standardization WG (M. Gucciardo – IMDEA)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Open Smart Networks and Services WG (A. Garcia-Saavedra)
5G PPP whitepaper	"The European 5G Annual Journal 2023" by Marco Fiore (IMDEA)
5G PPP Book	"Towards Sustainable and Trustworthy 6G: Challenges, Enablers, and Architectural Design" by Marco Gramaglia, Xi Li, Andrés Garcia-Saavedra, Marco Fiore (UC3M, NEC, IMDEA)

2.3 Exploitation activities

2.3.1 Standardization activities

In this section, we provide an update of the standardization activities of the project for the third year and three-month extension (Y3). A detailed information of the standard activity contributions in Y1 and Y2 can be found in Deliverables 6.2 [2] and 6.3 [3] respectively.

The following Table 6 lists the approved SDO contributions that we have achieved in Y3.

Table 6. DAEMON SDO approved contributions during Y3.

Target SDO	Type of contribution (Date)	Partner	WG	Description of the contribution	Ration to DAEMON Innovations and use cases
O-RAN	Standard contribution (15 Dec 2022)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0026: Specify the requirements on capabilities in Non-RT RIC to support O-Cloud Monitoring services	Propose Non-RT RIC architecture extensions to enable CloudRIC solutions developed in WP3 and WP5 (reported in D3.3 and D5.3)
O-RAN	Standard contribution (20 Dec 2022)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0028: To clarify the relationship between O2 related functions and Federated O-Cloud Orchestration and Management (FOCOM), Network Function Orchestrator (NFO) and O2-related OAM functions	Propose O2 interface extensions to support CloudRIC solutions developed in WP3 and WP5 (reported in D3.3 and D5.3)

O-RAN	Standard contribution (17 Jan 2023)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0029: Add O2 deployment management service to allow the Service Consumer to obtain information related to O-Cloud deployment management services	Extend the capability of O2-deployment management services to obtain information from the O-Cloud, which can support CloudRIC solutions developed in WP3 and WP5 (reported in D3.3 and D5.3)
O-RAN	Standard contribution (15 Dec 2022)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0027: Specify the requirements on capabilities in Non-RT RIC to support collecting analytical data from the Near-RT RIC	To support the DAEMON NI services with the need for the Non-RT RIC to obtain the analytical data generated from the Near-RT RIC
O-RAN	Standard contribution (18 Jan 2023)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0030: Add AI/ML workflow services	To support the DAEMON NI services to be integrated with the AIML workflow services in Non-RT RIC: including: (1) AI/ML training service; (2) AI/ML model management and exposure service; (3) AI/ML model performance monitoring services
O-RAN	Standard contribution (02 Mar 2023)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0034: Add AI/ML model retrieve services	To enable the DAEMON NI services to be supported by the AI/ML model retrieve service, which allows an rApp to request model location details of a specific version of a registered AI/ML model
O-RAN	Standard contribution (02 Aug 2023)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0040: Add description on AI/ML model deployment	To support the DAEMON NI services, which require the AI/ML model deployment for an authorized rApp, that can request the deployment of a specific version of a registered AI/ML model
O-RAN	Standard contribution (26 Jun 2023)	NEC	WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR-0037: Introduce AI/ML model retrieval use case	To support the DAEMON NI services, in which an rApp needs to retrieve model location details as a consumer of registered AI/ML model(s)

During Y3, the DAEMON project made eight approved contributions to the O-RAN standard, which are mainly focusing on defining AI/ML support and workflow in O-RAN, including AI/ML model deployment and retrieve, data management, training, and monitoring services. These contributions stem from the need – emerged during the project execution – of supporting several functionalities of innovative NI services developed by DAEMON. More precisely, the first three ORAN contributions listed in Table 6 are

related to providing support to the O-Cloud and extending the O2 interface and O2-related functions to enable the integration of the CloudRIC solution, which has been developed in WP3 and WP5 (reported in D3.3 and D5.3) in DAEMON, into the O-RAN architecture framework.

2.3.2 Open-source activities

This section outlines the relevant open-source projects being leveraged in the DAEMON project, details the project GitHub, and highlights the main work concerning open-source activities during Y3.

2.3.2.1 Relevant large open-source projects

As highlighted in previous deliverables such as D6.3 [3], the project leverages two high-profile open-source software suites to help enabling the technological advancements proposed in the project. Specifically, srsRAN is used as the RAN platform, while Eclipse is used to provide edge computing platforms. srsRAN has over 3,500 stars on GitHub across both srsRAN 4G and srsRAN Project, while Eclipse has over 1,200 stars across both Zenoh and Zenoh-flow.

Over the course of the last year, DAEMON has made three additional contributions to one of the relevant open-source projects, i.e., Eclipse Zenoh. This brings the total number of contributions to external projects to 9 over the whole project's lifespan.

Table 7. DAEMON Open-source Contributions to external projects during Y3.

Type	Overview	Date	Open-source Project	Partner
Release	Contribution to Eclipse Zenoh release 0.7.0-rc	21/12/2022	Eclipse Zenoh	ZSCALE
Release	Contribution to Eclipse Zenoh release candidate v0.7.2-rc	06/06/2023	Eclipse Zenoh	ZSCALE
Release	Contribution to Eclipse Zenoh release candidate v0.10.0-r	27/09/2023	Eclipse Zenoh	ZSCALE

We next present the overall evolution and impact of the two large open-source projects targeted by DAEMON during the third year of execution of the action.

2.3.2.1.1 srsRAN

srsRAN 4G has been continuously developed during year 3 by SRS, including the release of their new 5G SA O-RAN native gNB, named srsRAN Project. This replaces the srsRAN 4G code base as the recommended open-source 5G RAN implementation. srsRAN Project follows the 3GPP 5G system architecture implementing the functional splits (e.g. Split 7.2x and 8) between Distributed Unit (DU), Centralized Unit (CU) and the Radio Unit (RU). The code base also implements many O-RAN-specific interfaces, such as the E2 interface. DAEMON has continued to contribute to the O-RAN WGs, specifically WG3 which focuses on the near-RT RIC specifications. These contributions will influence how SRS further develops the E2 interface, which connects the E2 agents within the RAN stack to the near-RT RIC. Since the beginning of the project the popularity of both srsRAN 4G and srsRAN Project has grown at a steady rate. Both projects now have over 3,000 stars between them on GitHub.

The evolution of the srsRAN Project and srsRAN 4G software in GitHub over the third year of execution of DAEMON is summarized in Figure 11 and Figure 12, in terms of their star history.

Figure 11. srsRAN Project Github star history in Y3.

Figure 12. srsRAN 4G Github star history in Y3.

2.3.2.1.2 Eclipse

The Eclipse Foundation has been DAEMON's strategic partner in the role of hosting the Zenoh's open-source project. This project has been continuously developed during the 3 years period of the duration of DAEMON. Figure 13 illustrates the increase in stars, which is directly related to the visibility of the Zenoh project from January 2021 (when the open-source tool had approximately 100 stars) until the end of DAEMON's project (by which time the project reached approximately 1,200 stars).

Figure 13. Eclipse Zenoh's Github star history in the last three years.

Besides this, part of the DAEMON innovations in decentralized monitoring of infrastructure have been integrated into Zenoh and will be used later in other domains such as robotics and software defined vehicles. The Open-Source Robotics Foundation performed a study and concluded that Zenoh best meets the requirements and will be chosen as an alternative middleware. Zenoh was also the most recommended alternative by ROS/ROS2 users¹. Eclipse Zenoh was identified as the most appropriate protocol for V2X applications for autonomous and assisted driving in the IUT-T FGAI4AD-01 Automated driving safety data protocol – Specification².

Finally, in the Eclipse Software Defined Vehicle (SDV) working group, Zenoh has been selected as one of the communication middleware in addition to MQTT³.

2.3.2.2 DAEMON GitHub

The DAEMON GitHub page received multiple updates during Y3, based on the recommendations during the second project review. Many of the tools and datasets used by the project and mentioned in papers, deliverables, and project demonstrations were open-sourced to allow members of the public to easily reproduce the work of the project. The project GitHub had until this point contained some assets, but more were added retrospectively and as they became available throughout Y3. In this way, the project results can be used by the wider scientific and industrial community as well as by the general public, ultimately ensuring the longevity and impact of the research beyond the end of the project.

In total, we have added 11 assets to GitHub during the last reporting period. These consist of tools (software applications, docker images) and datasets (used to train ML/AI models or the outputs of these models). They can be seen in the following table. These assets are also available on OpenAIRE and/or Zenodo. These new assets bring to 21 the total number of open-source applications, trained models, datasets and Kubernetes deployments made publicly available by DAEMON.

Table 8. List of assets added to the DAEMON GitHub. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.

Type	Name	Date published	Related WP or activity	Partner	URL
Tool	NEMO2 : a tool to Model and Transform by Bit-Blasting Numerical Feature Models into different Propositional Formulas and Universal Variability Language (UVL) Models	04/01/2023	A6	UMA	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Nemo2_tool

¹ <https://discourse.ros.org/uploads/short-url/o9ihvSiCwB8LkzRklpKdeesRTDi.pdf>

² https://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-t/opb/fg/T-FG-AI4AD-2022-PDF-E.pdf

³ <https://sdv.eclipse.org/projects/>

Tool	AutoManager: a Meta-Learning Model for Network Management from Intertwined Forecasts	20/01/2023	A32, A33	IMDEA, UC3M	https://github.com/h2020daemon/AutoManager
Tool	Flowrest: in-switch flow-level classification with random forests	30/01/2023	A18	IMDEA, UC3M	https://github.com/h2020daemon/Flowrest
Tool	K8s-open5GS: Kubernetes version of Open5Gs	16/02/2023	A29	UC3M	https://github.com/h2020daemon/k8s-open5gs
Tool	srsRAN_4G: Open source SDR 4G software suite from Software Radio Systems (SRS)	24/03/2023	WP2 – Task 2.4	SRS	https://github.com/h2020daemon/srsRAN_4G
Tool	Kansaa: Combining Deep Learning and Optimization for Practical Overbooking of Network Slices	21/09/2023	A31	IMDEA, UC3M	https://github.com/h2020daemon/kansaa
Dataset	SPLC22: Quality-aware Analysis and Optimisation of Virtual Network Functions	21/10/2023	A6	UMA	https://github.com/h2020daemon/SPLC22
Tool	Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits: A library to solve contextual bandit problems with hard constraints	15/12/2023	WP2 – Task2.4	NEC	https://github.com/h2020daemon/risk_aware_contextual_bandit
Tool	CloudRIC: Latency and energy consumption models of a CPU and a GPU LDPC decoder	22/02/2024	A2	NEC, IMDEA, UC3M, I2CAT	https://github.com/h2020daemon/CloudRIC
Dataset	CloudRIC Artifacts: Latency and energy consumption characterization of a CPU and a GPU LDPC decoder	26/02/2024	A2	NEC, IMDEA, UC3M, I2CAT	https://github.com/h2020daemon/CloudRic-Artifacts
Dataset	RIS power measurements: Experimental characterization of NEC Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface	26/02/2024	A23	NEC	https://github.com/h2020daemon/RIS-Power-Measurements-Dataset

Deliverable 5.3, Section 4 presents the open-source datasets and software developed in DAEMON and outlines the full list of tools and datasets that have been open-sourced by the project since the start of its activities. In that section, the associated activities within the project are also linked to each asset produced in Y1 and Y2, which was not an information available in deliverables produced in those years.

2.3.3 Academic activities

During Y3, we continued with the academic activities that we had previously started during Y1 and Y2 of the project. We further detail these activities in Table 9 below.

Table 9. Academic Activities during Y3.

Activity	Title	Academic entity
MSc Thesis	Online Learning for Edge Network Caching	TUD
PhD Thesis	Optimization Algorithms for Robust Network Intelligence	TUD
PhD Thesis	Energy-efficient tasks assignment for heterogeneous deployment architectures on Edge Computing	UMA
PhD Thesis	Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach	UMA
PhD Thesis	Network intelligence for resource management in 6G networks	IMDEA, UC3M
PhD Thesis	Tailoring machine learning for zero-touch network management	IMDEA, UC3M

PhD Thesis	Integration and demonstration of remote sensing functionalities in future-generation mobile network architectures	IMDEA, UC3M
Postdoctoral fellowship	Design and implementation of network intelligence in the user plane of 6G mobile networks	IMDEA
Postdoctoral fellowship	Tailoring of Artificial Intelligence models for network orchestration	IMDEA
MSc Course	5G Standards	UC3M
MSc Course	B5G Operation Requirements	TUD

2.3.4 Industrial exploitation activities

DAEMON defined a series of additional performance metrics, listed in Table 10, to be used throughout the lifetime of the project to capture its status in terms of exploitation of the work carried out during the action. As previously reported in D6.3, at the end of Y2 we had already achieved two of these three additional key industrial exploitation metrics, namely “*Number of new methods, tools, systems, services and processes supporting NI services provision*” and “*Number of commercially available and exploitable DAEMON NI tools and methods*” (as two of the innovation radar contributions were indeed already marked as “Tech Ready”, as we show in further detail in Table 14). In fact, one of these innovations published in the Innovation Radar (namely, **ANCHOR: Anomaly Detection Approach for the Roaming Platform**) progressed in the technology development process to become an actual pilot that we have executed together with Telefonica Global Solutions (as reported in detail in deliverable D5.3).

Finally, we have also explored the possibility of defining “*new business models developed to support native NI via DAEMON*”. Specifically, as a follow-up on the pilot we have performed for Activity A13, we are discussing with the business unit a novel business model that would support the potential tech transfer of the technology.

Table 10. Key Industrial Exploitation Metrics.

KPI	Target	Relevant initiatives for target
Number of new business models developed to support native NI via DAEMON	1	<i>Innovation in the business category</i>
Number of commercially available and exploitable DAEMON NI tools and methods	2	<i>Patented innovation tools and/or methods under exploitation within a business unit</i>
Number of new methods, tools, systems, services, and processes supporting NI services provision	3	<i>The main areas of innovation we aim to address correspond to the NI-assisted functionalities addressed by DAEMON</i>

2.3.4.1 Innovation Radar

As previously presented in D6.3 [3], DAEMON generated five main innovations which were already included in the Innovation Radar initiative⁴ of the European Commission. An overview of the innovations accepted by the Innovation Radar is later provided in Section 3.2, and specifically in Table 14.

2.3.4.2 Patents

During Y3, DAEMON submitted two new patent applications related to technical activities in the project, which we detail in Table 11. With these additional filed patents, the project achieves a total of nine patent applications related to activities that we have performed in DAEMON. This falls short of the initial target of 20 patents, and it is the single KPI target that is not met by the project by the end of its execution.

Table 11. DAEMON patent applications during Y3.

Patent title	Owner	Sector	Market/Stakeholder	Status
A method for proactive anomaly detection for IoT connectivity in global roaming	TID	Industry	Telco	Filed
Methods and procedures to enable ML-model training in the O-RAN O-cloud	NEC	Industry	5G	Filed

⁴ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

2.3.5 Event highlights

DAEMON hosted meetings and booths in several venues during Y3. We detail 10 of these events below.

2.3.5.1 *Mobile World Congress 2023*

The two H2020-ICT-52 projects DAEMON and AI@EDGE, both part of 5G PPP, shared a stand at the **Mobile World Congress (MWC) 2023** in Barcelona, Spain. MWC is attended by global mobile operators, device manufacturers, technology providers, vendors, and content owners, and is widely regarded as one of the major events of the year for the telco ecosystem at large. The stand displayed multiple technologies developed in DAEMON, including a live demonstrator of the Flowrest solution for ultra-low latency NI in the programmable user plane, which attracted a lot of attention by the many visitors of such a crowded event like MWC.

Figure 14. DAEMON booth at MWC 2023, with demos of the NI services developed by the project.

2.3.5.2 *DAEMON first industry workshop*

DAEMON organised its half-day **first DAEMON industry workshop**, including a complimentary brunch, at the premises of the consortium partner Telefonica I+D in Barcelona, Spain. The purpose was to present the vision and main results of the project, and to foster knowledge and discussions among industry representatives around topics like beyond 5G, 6G, RAN virtualization, RIS, network orchestration, and AI-enabled network management. It took place during 9:30-13:30 of April 21, 2023. The complete program, featuring a number of industry partners outside the consortium, and all further details about the event are available in <https://h2020daemon.eu/industry-workshop-2023/>.

Figure 15. Natalia Romankevic (Net AI) presenting at the DAEMON first Industry workshop.

2.3.5.3 *ANMS 2023 workshop*

DAEMON organized the **2nd International Workshop on Autonomous Network Management in 5G and Beyond Systems (ANMS 2023)** which focuses on novel research in algorithms for the management of Autonomous Network (Ans) in B5G systems. More specifically, we encouraged original paper submissions from academia and industry presenting novel research on the most recent advances, frameworks, models, and approaches for management of autonomous networks using enabling techniques like SDN, AI, and blockchain. It was collocated with Collocated with 2023 IEEE/IFIP Network Operations and Management Symposium (NOMS). It took place in Miami (Florida, USA) during 8 to 12 May 2023. All the information is available at <https://h2020daemon.eu/workshop-anms-2023/>.

Figure 16. Miguel Camelo Botero (IMEC) chairing a session of the DAEMON-supported ANMS 2023.

2.3.5.4 EuCNC 2023

DAEMON was present in a booth at the **2023 edition of the European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC)** in Gothenburg (Sweden). The conference was sponsored by the IEEE Communications Society (ComSoc), the European Association for Signal Processing (EURASIP) and the European Association on Antennas and Propagation (EurAAP). The event focuses on all aspects of telecommunications ranging from 5G deployment and mobile IoT to 6G exploration and future communications systems and networks, including experimentation and testbeds, and applications and services. It brings together cutting-edge research and world-renown industries and businesses, globally attracting in the last years more than 900 delegates from more than 40 countries all over the world, to present and discuss the latest results, and an exhibition with more than 50 exhibitors, for demonstrating the technology developed in the area, namely within research projects from EU R&I programmes.

At EuCNC 2023, DAEMON also co-organized its **second industry workshop on “Exploring the Intersection of 6G and Artificial Intelligence: Unleashing the Potential of Next-Gen Technologies”**, jointly with a number of other H2020 projects. The workshops aligned a program of industry talks that explored the intersection of artificial intelligence (AI) and 6G technology: the complete program of the workshop is available at <https://www.eucnc.eu/programme/workshops/workshop-5/>. As 6G is the next generation of mobile networks that promises to revolutionize the way we connect and interact with the world around us thanks to high-speed, low-latency, and high-bandwidth capabilities. The workshop talks explored the potential of 6G to enable new and exciting use cases in a variety of industries, including transportation, healthcare, and manufacturing, as well as how AI can drive innovation in a wide range of fields, including computer vision, natural language processing, and decision-making. The discussions then focused on how AI and 6G can work together to create new business opportunities and support new application verticals, as well as the challenges and opportunities that lie ahead. The workshop was a good experience for researchers, engineers, and industry professionals to learn about the latest developments in AI and 6G and to network with other experts in the field. It also provided a platform for attendees to share their own research and ideas, and to explore potential collaborations.

Figure 17. DAEMON stand at the EuCNC 2023 conference.

2.3.5.5 IEEE ICC 2023

DAEMON hold a booth in the **Industry Forum at the IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC) 2023** in Rome, Italy. IEEE ICC is one of two IEEE Communications Society's flagship conferences (ICC and Globecom). Each year, close to 2,000 attendees from over 70 countries attend IEEE ICC to take advantage of a program which consists of exciting keynote session, robust technical paper sessions, innovative tutorials and workshops, and engaging industry sessions. This 5-day event is known for bringing together audiences from both industry and academia to learn about the latest research and innovations in communications and networking technology, share ideas and best practices, and collaborate on future projects.

Figure 18. DAEMON booth at the Industry Forum of the IEEE ICC 2023 conference.

2.3.5.6 IEEE NetSoft 2023

DAEMON showcased the Flowrest demonstration at the **2023 IEEE International Conference on Network Softwarization (NetSoft)** in Madrid, Spain, <https://netsoft2023.ieee-netsoft.org/program/demo-sessions>. The theme of the IEEE NetSoft 2023 "Boosting Future Networks through Advanced Softwarization" reflects the vision that future networks will also integrate a native service dimension in a continuum compute-connectivity environment crossing different network segments/providers/domains and enabled by softwarization coupled with new advanced architectures, frameworks, and models. This will allow greater flexibility, reliability, adaptability, and efficiency for both network operations and service deployments for the benefit of an ecosystem of different application layers/developers/components. This will also lay the foundation to head beyond the current inter-networking capabilities in Future Internet architectures and to further convergence between internetworking and IP layer re-engineering.

It is to be noted that the DAEMON demonstrator won the Best Demo Award at this event.

Figure 19. DAEMON showcasing the Flowrest demo at IEEE NetSoft 2023, and the received award.

2.3.5.7 Embrace Equity 2023

DAEMON supported the initiative **Embrace Equity 2023** from Women in Telecommunications and Research (WiTaR), honouring our female members and supporters.

Figure 20. DAEMON supporting WiTaR 2023.

2.3.5.8 NetMob 2023 Data Challenge

DAEMON supported the organization and running of the data challenge associated to the NetMob 2024 conference. The **NetMob 2023 Data Challenge** was a competition aiming at deriving and exploiting insights from massive mobile service consumption information. Proposals addressed one of the following three topics: (i) understanding social challenges through the lenses of mobile service usage; (ii) generating reliable datasets of synthetic mobile data traffic; and, (iii) automating network management with data-driven intelligence. This last point was the one most related with the DAEMON activities, and therefore the reason why the project supported the data challenge. In this way, DAEMON contributed to the design of data-driven solutions for beyond-5G mobile network ecosystem, and to the use of machine learning models as a promising tool to address many complex network management tasks, including forecasting of mobile demand and throughput, infrastructure planning, orchestration of network slices, classification of flow-level traffic or control of virtualized RAN resources. Overall, 11 talks and 33 posters were presented during the data challenge session of NetMob 2023. <https://netmob2023challenge.networks.imdea.org/>.

Figure 21. Pictures from the session dedicated to the data challenge during the NetMob 2023 conference. Left: welcome message acknowledging the DAEMON project as a supporting initiative of the data challenge, and awarding of the winning contribution based on the dataset.

2.3.5.9 ConfWS 2023 Workshop

DAEMON organized the **25th International Workshop on Configuration (ConfWS 2023)** which took place in Universidad de Málaga, Spain during 6-7 September 2023. Besides researchers from a variety of configuration-related fields, the workshop has always attracted a significant number of participants from industry (major configurator vendors as well as application developers). The main goal of the workshop was to promote high-quality research in all technical areas related to configuration and to bring together

researchers and practitioners from industry and academia. The workshop was of interest for both researchers working in the various fields of applicable technologies and industry representatives interested in the relationship between configuration technology and the business problem behind configuration and mass customization.

Figure 22. Best Paper Awards at UMA premises in the DAEMON-supported ConfWS'23 workshop.

2.3.5.10 Infocom World Conference 2023

The **25th Infocom World Conference**, held as an fully in-person event in Athens, Greece, on December 14, 2023, (<https://infocomworld.gr/>) has been considered “the greatest ICT & Media Conference in South-Eastern Europe” and it is regarded as “the major annual meeting of all the digital market stakeholders” in order to implement digital transformation, conformant to current market needs and related challenges and especially contributing to the effort for creating a fully digital Greece.

The Infocom World Conference 2023 brought forth progress and innovation in the telecommunications and IT sectors, and technology in general. This year, the conference was the crossroads of the past, present and future, as it marked 30 years of mobile telephony in Greece, as well as 25 years of Infocom World history. It also focused on Artificial Intelligence, highlighting its most important aspects, the value of its applications, and the effect it now has on all vertical markets. With a line-up of influential speakers, Infocom World was a meeting place for industry leaders, researchers, policymakers and entrepreneurs, showcasing the transformative potential of connectivity and the future of telecommunications,

DAEMON had a strong presence with a booth in the main exhibition centre of Infocom World 2022, organized by OTE. This can be seen Figure 21.

Figure 23. Infocom World Conference 2023 website landing page.

Figure 24. DAEMON booth at the Infocom World Conference 2023.

3 Communication, dissemination, exploitation KPIs over the whole project

In this section, we provide a succinct overview of the DAEMON consortium achievements through the duration of the project in terms of communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. We provide in Table 12 a final count of the most important KPIs that we collected related to these activities.

Table 12. Overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation KPIs over the whole project.

Objective 5	SDO contributions	Patents	Contributions to large open-source projects	Industry events attended	Industrial workshops organized	Demos	Pilots
Industrial KPIs							
Final status	45 / 30	9 / 20	8 / 6	10 / 10	2 / 2	9 / 4	2 / 0
Progress in Y3 *	8 **	2	3	2	2	6	2
Achieved	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

Objective 5	Scientific workshops organized	Scientific journal Special Issues edited	Scientific publications ***	Scientific publications in top-tier venues ****	Open-source assets
Scientific KPIs					
Final status	7 / 2	3 / 2	116 / 80	39 / 20	20 / 0
Progress in Y3 *	1	2	52	25	11
Achieved	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y

* Progress is assessed with respect to figures reported in D1.3 of the DAEMON project.

** Based on comments received during the second project review, we removed 2 SDO contributions to the IRTF that were included in Y2 deliverables.

*** Scientific publications include all peer-reviewed papers, hence conference, workshop, and journal publications. Instead, they do not include books, chapters, and whitepaper publications.

**** We highlight here the total number of top-tier publications in highly competitive venues, i.e., journals in JCR first quartile (Q1) and in conference listed as A/A* in the CORE ranking. These publications are a subset of the scientific publication in the previous column and are listed separately in Section 3.1 as per comments received during the second project review.

3.1 Dissemination and communication activities

In terms of **communication KPIs** in numbers over the duration of the project, we report the following.

- We committed to publishing 2 press releases per year, and produced 3 press releases in Y3, including one that will be published after the end of the action.
- We committed to organizing a total of 2 academic workshops/conferences and accomplished this by organizing 1 event in Y3 for a total of 7 scientific events organized.
- We committed to organizing 2 and participating in 10 industrial events, and in Y3 we organized both project industrial workshops and attended the two outstanding industrial events.
- We committed to advertising our website to reach over 75% of the visits from outside of the consortium, and it is currently above that number considering the ones from USA, China or UK.

Also part of the communication activities, although not an explicit KPI, the consortium produced by the end of the project 20 videos, included one professionally recorded promotional video for the DAEMON YouTube channel and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215978>). In previous years, we also produced PowerPoint slides from conference presentations that were uploaded to the DAEMON Zenodo community, and a project brochure. All assets related to project communication are populated and monitored in the DAEMON OpenAIRE profile.

In terms of **dissemination KPIs** over the whole duration of the DAEMON project, we report the following.

- We committed to providing a total of 80 publications, and since the beginning of the project we have accumulated 41 Journals, 6 magazines, 59 conferences, 10 workshops, 6 whitepapers, 7 demonstration papers, 2 PhD Thesis, 1 book, 1 book chapter, 1 scientific poster and 9 slides, which

sums up to a total of 133 publications to date including the 9 presentation slide-decks. If we limit the count to peer-reviewed papers, DAEMON generated 116 publications. Y3 was especially productive, going beyond the already high bars set in Y1 and Y2 and leading to the issuing of 52 new conference, journal, or workshop publications.

- We committed to publishing a total of 4 demonstrations, and in Y3 the project produced 6 additional demos, leading to a total of 9 operational demonstrations to date.
- We committed to editing 2 Special Issues of scientific journals, and the project partners co-edited 2 such Special Issues in Y3, thus exceeding the initial target 3 Special Issues edited by the end of the project, in addition to the co-editing of 1 book that was not foreseen initially.

Beyond the KPIs listed above, one consideration is especially important in the opinion of the DAEMON consortium, as also stressed during previous project reviews by the comments received. The project had originally set an ambitious target of 20 publications in top-tier scientific venues, which are defined in an objective manner as conferences ranked A or A* in the CORE Ranking⁵ or journals listed in the first quartile (Q1) of the JCR.

The project largely exceeded expectations in that sense, with 10 publications at top-tier conferences in Y3 as well as 15 publications in top-tier journals in Y3. These figures imply that DAEMON has largely exceeded its objective in terms of high-quality publications with a total number of 39 top-tier papers that almost double the initial target.

As per requests received during the second project review, a complete list of all top-tier publications produced by DAEMON during its lifetime is presented in Table 13 and Table 14.

Table 13. List of publications in top-tier conferences during project lifetime. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.

Date Tasks	Title	Event	Authors	Related WP or activity	Open access DOI
21/10	Nuberu: Reliable RAN Virtualization in Shared Platforms	ACM MobiCom 2021	G. Garcia-Aviles, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Gramaglia, X. Costa-Perez, P. Serrano, A. Banchs (UC3M, NEC, IMDEA)	A1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5599123
21/08 T4.2	Insights from Operating an IP Exchange Provider	ACM SIGCOMM 2021	A. Lutu, D. Perino, M. Bagnulo, F.E. Bustamante (TID)	A19	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5722464
21/02 T2.4	CloudLSTM: A Recurrent Neural Model for Spatiotemporal Point-cloud Stream Forecasting	AAAI 2021	C. Zhang, M. Fiore, I. Murray, P. Patras (IMDEA)	WP2 – Task 2.4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5524838
22/05 T4.2	Global mobile network aggregators: taxonomy, roaming performance and optimization	ACM MobiSys 2022	Sergi Alcalá-Marín, Aravindh Raman, Weili Wu, Andra Lutu, Marcelo Bagnulo, Ozgu Alay, Fabian E. Bustamante (TID, IMDEA, UC3M)	A13	https://doi.org/10.1145/3498361.3538942
22/05 T2.3	LossLeaP: Learning to Predict for Intent-Based Networking	IEEE INFOCOM 2022	A. Collet, A. Banchs, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	WP2 – Task 2.3	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351613
23/01 T3.4 T5.2	Flowrest: Practical Flow-Level Inference in Programmable Switches with Random Forests	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A.T.-J. Akem, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550150

⁵ <https://portal.core.edu.au/conf-ranks/>

23/01 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	AutoManager: a Meta-Learning Model for Network Management from Intertwined Forecasts	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A. Collet, A. Bazco Nogueras, A. Banchs, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A32, A33	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550176
23/01 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	Spotting Deep Neural Network Vulnerabilities in Mobile Traffic Forecasting with an Explainable AI Lens	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	S. Moghadas, C. Fiandrino, A. Collet, G. Attanasio, M. Fiore, J. Widmer (IMDEA, UC3M)	A25	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550186
23/05 T3.1 T5.2	Spotlight on 5G: Performance, Device Evolution and Challenges from a Mobile Operator Perspective	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	P. Parastar, A. Lutu, O. Alay, G. Caso, D. Perino (TID)	A13	https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOCOM53939.2023.10229108
23/03 T4.2	Reservation of Virtualized Resources with Optimistic Online Learning	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	Jean Baptiste Monteil; George Iosifidis; Ivana Dusparic (TUD)	A14	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134360
23/10 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	kaNSaaS: Combining Deep Learning and Optimization for Practical Overbooking of Network Slices	ACM MobiHoc 2023	Sergi Alcalá-Marín, Antonio Bazco-Nogueras, Albert Banchs, Marco Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A31	https://www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10017773
23/12 T3.3	Data-driven Analysis of the Cost-Performance Trade-off of Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces in a Production Network	ACM CoNEXT 2023	M. Rossanese, A. Garcia-Saavedra, A. Lutu, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, TID)	A23	https://doi.org/10.1145/3629134
24/05 T3 T1	Mean-Field Multi-Agent Contextual Bandit for Energy-Efficient Resource Allocation in vRANs	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Lo-Schiavo, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, IMDEA, i2CAT)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686512
24/05 T3 T1	OREO: O-RAN intelligence Orchestration of xApp-based network services	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	F. Mungari, C. Puligheddu, A. Garcia-Saavedra, C. F. Chiasserini (NEC)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686449
24/05 T3 T1	YinYangRAN: Resource Multiplexing in GPU-Accelerated Virtualized RANs	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	L. Lo Schiavo, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Fiore, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, IMDEA, i2CAT)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686545
24/05 T3 T1	ORANUS: Latency-tailored Orchestration via Stochastic Network Calculus in 6G ORAN	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	O. Adamuz-Hinojosa, L. Zanzi, V. Sciancalepore, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, i2CAT)	A5	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.03812
24/05 T3 T1	Risk-Aware Continuous Control with Neural Contextual Bandits	AAAI 2024	J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	WP2 – Task2.4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686581

24/09 T3 T1	CloudRIC: Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) Virtualization with Shared Heterogeneous Computing	ACM MobiCom 2024	L. Lo Schiavo, G. Garcia-Aviles, A. Garcia-Saavedra, M. Gramaglia, M. Fiore, A. Banchs, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, I2CAT, IMDEA, UC3M)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10693534
24/06 T4.1 T4.2	Fair Resource Allocation in Virtualized O-RAN Platforms	ACM SIGMETRICS 2024	F. Aslan, G. Iosifidis, J. A. Ayala-Romero, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC, TUD)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10686646
24/05 T3.4 T5.2	Jewel: Resource-Efficient Joint Packet and Flow Level Inference in Programmable Switches	IEEE INFOCOM 2024	A.T.-J. Akem, B. Bütün, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A18	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10731523

Table 14. List of publications in top-tier journals during project lifetime. Dates are in YY/MM format. Activities are listed in D5.3 of the DAEMON project.

Date Tasks	Title	Journal	Authors	Related WP or activity	Open access DOI
20/07 T3.2	RadiOrchestra: Proactive Management of Millimeter-wave Self-backhauled Small Cells via Joint Optimization of Beamforming, User Association, Rate Selection, and Admission Control	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	Luis F. Abanto-Leon, Arash Asadi, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Gek Hong (Allyson) Sim, Matthias Hollick (NEC)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974569
22/08 T3.2	Migration-Aware Network Services with Edge Computing	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	Atri Mukhopadhyay, George Iosifidis, and Marco Ruffini (TUD)	A14	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038273
22/09 T5.1 T5.2 T5.3	Design and Validation of an Open Source Cloud Native Mobile Network	IEEE Communications Magazine	Nikolaos Apostolakis, Marco Gramaglia, Pablo Serrano (UC3M)	A29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7053585
22/05 T4.1 T4.4 T5.2	Selective Edge Computing for Mobile Analytics	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	Apostolos Galanopoulos; George Iosifidis; Theodoros Salonidis; Douglas J. Leith (TUD)	A17	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565476
23/06 T2.2 T4.4	Network Intelligence for NFV scaling in closed-loop architectures	IEEE Communications Magazine	P. Soto, M. Camelo, D. De Vleeschauwer, Y. De Bock, C.-Y. Chang, J.F. Botero, S. Latré (IMEC, NOKIA)	A16	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7705141
23/10 T2.2	O-RAN: Analysis of Latency-critical Interfaces and Overview of Time Sensitive Networking Solutions	IEEE Communications Standards Magazine	Esteban Municio, Gines Garcia-Aviles, Andres Garcia-Saavedra and Xavier Costa-Pérez (I2CAT, NEC)	A2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021416

23/04 T4.4	Deep Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning with Minimal Cross-Agent Communication for SFC Partitioning	IEEE Access	Angelos Pentelas, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Chia-Yu Chang, Koen De Schepper, Panagiotis Papadimitriou (NBL)	A30	https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3269576
23/04 T4.1	EdgeBOL: A Bayesian Learning Approach for the Joint Orchestration of vRANs and Mobile Edge AI	IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking	Jose A. Ayala-Romero; Andres Garcia-Saavedra; Xavier Costa-Pérez; George Iosifidis (NEC, TUD)	A5	https://doi.org/10.1109/TNET.2023.3268981
23/09 T2.2 T2.4	Digital Twins for Next-Generation Mobile Networks: Applications and Solutions	IEEE Communications Magazine	Apostolakis, Nikolaos; Chatzieleftheriou, Livia Elena; Bega, Dario; Gramaglia, Marco; Banchs, Albert (UC3M, IMDEA)	A29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7913097
23/01 T4.4	Quid pro Quo in Streaming Services: Algorithms for Cooperative Recommendations	IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing	Dimitra Tsigkari; George Iosifidis; Akis Spyropoulos (TU Delft)	A27	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134257
23/01 T4.2	Lazy Lagrangians for Optimistic Learning With Budget Constraints	IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking	Daron Anderson; George Iosifidis; Douglas J. Leith (TU Delft)	WP2 – Task2.4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8134298
23/09 T3.1	Open Radio Access Networks (O-RAN) Experimentation Platform: Design and Datasets	IEEE Communications Magazine	J. Xavier-Salvat, J. A. Ayala-Romero, L. Zanzi, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	A4	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10021480
23/09 T2.2 T2.4	Data-centric Service-Based Architecture for Edge-Native 6G Network	IEEE Communications Magazine	Gabriele Baldoni, Jose Quevedo, Carlos Guimaraes, Antonio de la Oliva, Angelo Corsaro (ZSCALE)	WP2 - Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8335532
23/10 T2.4	Network Automation and Data Analytics in 3GPP 5G Systems	IEEE Network	Miguel Angel Garcia-Martin, Marco Gramaglia, Pablo Serrano (UC3M)	WP2 – Task 2.1	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8422077
23/10 T2.2 T3.3	AI-Empowered Management and Orchestration of Vehicular Systems in the Beyond 5G Era	IEEE Network	Nina Slamnik-Kriještorac, Miguel Camelo, Chia-Yu Chang, Paola Soto, Luca Cominardi, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Steven Latré, Johann M. Marquez-Barja (IMEC, NBL, ZSCALE)	A30	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10082536

23/11 T3 T1	ATHENA: Machine Learning and Reasoning for Radio Resources Scheduling in vRAN systems	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications	Apostolakis, N., Gramaglia, M., Chatzieleftheriou, L. E., Subramanya, T., Banchs, A., & Sanneck, H. (UC3M, IMDEA)	A29	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10183985
23/12 T4.3	AIRIC: Orchestration of Virtualized Radio Access Networks with Noisy Neighbours	IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications	J. Xavier Salvat, A. Garcia-Saavedra, X. Li, X. Costa-Perez (NEC)	A24	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10353739
23/12 T2.2	Designing the Network Intelligence Stratum for 6G Networks	Computer Networks {under review}	P. Soto et al. (IMEC, i2CAT, UC3M, WINGS, NOKIA, IMDEA, UMA, TID, ZSCALE, NEC)	WP2 – Task 2.2	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10619439
23/03 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	Explainable and Transferable Loss Meta-Learning for Zero-Touch Anticipatory Network Management	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	A. Collet, A. Bazco-Nogueras, A. Banchs, M. Fiore (IMDEA, UC3M)	A32	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10821655

3.2 Exploitation activities

In terms of exploitation results, the DAEMON project largely exceeded its original targets for KPIs related to demonstrations, with 6 new demos produced in Y3 that brought the total to 9 against an objective of 4, as reported in Table 12. Moreover, the project generated a large number of open-source assets that were not foreseen at the beginning of the action.

The highlight of the exploitation results is however another one, i.e., the fact that two solutions developed within DAEMON have reached a maturity unexpectedly quickly, leading two pilots consisting of industry-ready prototypes deployed in production-grade environments. These two pilots were not planned in the original exploitation KPIs of the project, and thus represent significant evidence of the success of the action in going beyond its initial commitments. The design of the two pilots was carried out in WP3 (Activity 13) and WP4 (Activity 19) and their implementation is detailed in Section 5 of D5.3.

The project was also successful and exceeded expectations in terms of the number of contributions to standardization. Specifically, Table 15 summarizes all the approved SDO contributions since the start of the project until the end of Y3, for a total 45 contributions to SDOs like O-RAN, ETSI, 3GPP and ITU-T.

Table 15. DAEMON SDO approved contributions since the start of the project to the end of Y3.

SDO	WGs	Partner	Number of contributions	Summary of contributions
O-RAN	WG 2 WG 3	NEC NBL	27	Non-RT RIC and near-RT RIC architectural design extensions to support for data collection and management, support for thesdo AIML workflow and model deployment. Non-RT RIC arch extensions for the proposed Cloud-RIC solutions developed in WP3 and WP5 (reported in D3.3 and D5.3)
ETSI RIS	RIS ISG	NEC	11	RIS support: scenarios, use cases and corresponding requirements
ETSI NFV	TID	TID	1	Contributions to the NFV ISG conversations based on the work we have performed in WP3/WP4 related to the intelligent approach of the virtual function placement within the environment of an operator.
ETSI ZSM	ZSM ISG	TID	1	DGR/ZSM-015_NDT: Network Digital Twin work item https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/ReportWorkitem.asp?WKI_ID=64372
3GPP	SA2	NBL	2	Study on XR (Extended Reality) and media services
ITU-T	FG-AN	UC3M	2	NI use cases definition

ITU-T	FGAI4 AD-01	ZSCALE	1	Automated driving safety data protocol Specification: Eclipse Zenoh identified as a suitable protocol for V2X applications for autonomous and assisted driving.
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During its lifetime, DAEMON contributed five different innovations to the Innovation Radar initiative of the European Commission, which we include in Table 16. These five innovations correspond to different areas that we identified and cover in DAEMON (in WP3 and WP4), and they are part of the guarantees of the impact of the project beyond its termination.

Table 16. DAEMON Innovations included in the Innovation Radar.

ID	Innovation name	Activity	Partner	Innovation type	Level of Innovation	Exploitation Strategy
1	ANCHOR: Anomaly Detection Approach for the Roaming Platform ⁶	A19	TID	New product	Very innovative	Only deployed as new to the organization/company (new internal processes implemented, etc.)
2	Reliable DU design suitable for virtualization ⁷	A1	NEC	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
3	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-based system to manage multiple wired connections in data centers ⁸	A23	NEC	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
4	Compute-aware RAN orchestrator (O-RAN Non-RT RIC differentiator) ⁹	A2	NEC	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
5	Classifier for video, data, gaming traffic ¹⁰	A3	NBL	Significantly improved product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)

The only KPI that could not be reached by the end of the project is the one related to patenting. A total of nine patents was filed that relate directly to activities that performed in WP3 and WP4. This is below the target of 20 set initially. This is due to an overestimation of the capabilities of the consortium to produce a large number of patents in the relatively short time frame of three years: indeed, the need to develop a technology mature enough to be patented plus the long patent filing process did not fit a 39-month period for most of the NI solutions devised in the project. Many additional innovations designed in the DAEMON project are expected translate into patents after the end of the action, yet those will not count towards achieving the KPI. The DAEMON partners compensated via additional effort on the other impacts, e.g., those related to dissemination and demonstration, for which KPIs were largely exceeded.

⁶ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46063>

⁷ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46064>

⁸ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46062>

⁹ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46061>

¹⁰ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46060>

A summary of the patents filed during the overall action is provided in Table 17.

Table 17. Summary of the patents filed based on DAEMON solutions by the end of its execution.

Patent title	Owner	Sector	Market or stakeholder	Activity	Status
A method for proactive anomaly detection for IoT connectivity in global roaming	TID	Industry	Telco	A19	Filed
Methods and procedures to enable ML-model training in the O-RAN O-cloud	NEC	Industry	5G	A4, A5	Filed
Reinforcement Learning-based method for automatic distributed optimization of cellular networks	TID	Industry	Telco	A13	Filed
Unsupervised clustering approach for identifying device patterns and requirements for network orchestration	TID	Industry	Telco	A13	Filed
A method to mitigate the noisy neighbours problem in vRAN deployments configuring the different units' placement and its functional split	NEC	Industry	5G	A29	Filed
A computer-implemented method for detecting anomalous behaviors of electronic devices and computer programs thereof	TID	Industry	Telco	A19	Filed
Real-Time and Energy-efficient Control of vRAN Resources in Shared O-RAN Clouds	NEC	Industry	5G	A2	Filed
Non-Real Time CloudRIC: Energy-efficient Control of vRAN Resources in Shared O-RAN Clouds	NEC	Industry	5G	A2	Filed
Methods and procedures to enable ML-model training in the O-RAN O-cloud	NEC	Industry	5G	A4, A5, A29	Filed

4 Exploitation plan for after the project

In this section, we detail the exploitation plans for after the project, which we aim to implement to ensure the impact of the project beyond its duration. This builds upon the previous work we reported in the WP2 Deliverables D2.1 [15], D2.2 [16], and D2.3 [17], the WP3 deliverables D3.1 [18], D3.2 [9], D3.3 [12], the WP4 deliverables D4.2 [10], D4.3 [13] and, finally, the WP5 deliverables D5.2 [11] and D5.3 [14].

4.1 Exploitation plans for individual partners and project activities

4.1.1 Vendors and service providers

Table 18. Exploitation plan for vendors and service providers.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
NEC	<p>The long-term exploitation plan was reported in D6.1 [1]. In brief, NEC plans to use the results and findings from DAEMON to evolve the current vRAN and O-RAN product portfolio, and to develop an added-value management and orchestration platform that brings the flexibility of SDN/NFV to NEC line of products, impacting the Mobile Radio Access Networks and Mobile Wireless Networking business units.</p> <p>In more detail, Activities A1 (D3.3 [12], Section 3.1; D5.3, Section 3.2.1), and A2 (D3.3 [12], Section 3.3; D5.3 [14], Section 3.2.2) have already impacted on the SDO plan of NEC, with a number of contributions implemented therein already. Correspondingly, these solutions will be considered by the corresponding NEC Business Unit for the next roadmap of NEC RAN virtualization solutions. Activities A4 (D4.3[13], Section 3.3; D5.3[14], Section 3.3.1), and A5 (D4.3[13], Section 3.4; D5.3[14], Section 3.3.2), seek improving NEC’s management and orchestration platform and the ideas within such activities will be exported to NEC Business Units to improve the energy efficiency of NEC O-RAN products, some of them in the current roadmap (RU energy savings), some others for a future roadmap (joint RAN and edge optimization). In the context of these activities, NEC has filed 5 patents, protecting NEC’s exploitation activities. Finally, Activity 23 (D3.3[12], Section 5; D5.3[14], Section 3.8) has inspired the seed for a new Reconfiguration Intelligent Surface product portfolio at NEC Corporation.¹¹ An early-bird prototype just began commercialization for research purposes.¹² Three of the above activities have been included in the Innovation Radar, which will help on commercialization.</p>
NBL	<p>On the one hand, the AIML algorithms being developed in DAEMON are instrumental for many Nokia network management and orchestration products that envision using AIML. These AIML models, e.g., SLA decomposition, VNF placement, traffic characterization, are gradually being built in many products (see Table 19). Concretely, the following plan is set forth by NBL for exploitation of the results.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The SLA decomposition problem in D2.1 [15] Section 6.2.1 and its solution in D6.3 Table 1 was already demonstrated to potential customers. • Activity A3 (D3.1, Section 4.3; D5.1, Section 4.1.3; D3.2 Section 2.3; D5.2, Section 4.1.3; D3.3, Section 3.4, D5.3, Section 3.2.3) has been used to classify various types of traffic in an application aware RAN PoC. • Activity 16 (D4.1, Section 6.2, D4.2, Section 5.2; D4.3, Section 6.2; D5.1, Section 4.4.7; D5.2, Section 4.4.7, D5.3, Section 3.5.5) are envisioned to improve efficiency of the future 6G products. It is expected that the results of this joint activity with IMEC will have impact on the roadmap a few years from now. • Activity A30 (D4.1, Section 6.1; D4.2, Section 5.1; D5.2, Section 4.2.6, D5.3, Section 3.3.6) have been discussed with the relevant Business Unit. Simplified versions have already been demoed to customers. The more elaborated versions will be implemented as soon as the AI capabilities of the platform allows. <p>On the other hand, a native AIML architecture that DAEMON developed in WP2, can be used as guideline for a future 6G architecture. Activity A.3 has been included in the Innovation Radar, which helps raising interest for the PoC.</p>

¹¹ <https://www.neclab.eu/about-us/press-releases/detail/nec-laboratories-europe-achieves-breakthrough-in-smart-surface-technology-for-5g-and-beyond-wireless-connectivity>

¹² <https://www.youris.io/prototype/>

4.1.2 Network operators

Table 19. Exploitation plan for network operators.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
TID	<p>TID supports the transfer of the technology we have developed within DAEMON to the industrial sector mainly through internal collaborations with business units within the Telefonica corporation. Specifically, we have been working closely with Virgin Media O2 (WMO2) in the UK and with Telefonica Global Solutions (TGS) in Spain. Together with each of these two business units, we have run two pilots for solutions that we have developed as part of DAEMON, corresponding to Activity 13 (D5.3, Section 3.5.1) and Activity 19 (D5.3, Section 3.4.2). We are currently continuing these collaborations and plan to further develop the NI solutions beyond the end of the project.</p> <p>Activity 19 was also reported as an innovation in the Innovation Radar, which will help gather more visibility and support.</p> <p>Moreover, building upon the interaction around the pilot for Activity A13, we are exploring new business models for NI that would allow us to perform the tech transfer for the solution to the interested business unit.</p> <p>The activities in DAEMON generated a total of four patent that are currently under evaluation.</p> <p>Moreover, TID communicated the activities within DAEMON internally to all the division of the Chief Digital Officer (CDO) of Telefónica as part of the internal TEFCon held in December 2023, ensuring a wider exposure to relevant teams internally within the Telefónica area.</p> <p>By participating in events such as the Dagstuhl Seminar 23222 on “Novel Scenarios for the Wireless Internet of Things”, TID have presented DAEMON results within a collaborative international forum with top industrial and academic audiences, meant to foster further collaboration on relevant topics.</p> <p>Finally, the tight collaboration between TID and members of the DAEMON consortium continues as part of new EU-funded projects (e.g., SNS projects where TID participates).</p>
OTE	<p>OTE communicated the activities within DAEMON internally informing the strategic partners of OTE & DT Group about the new findings and investigating their adoption within the commercial networks. OTE accelerated the development and deployment of modern and innovative NI functionalities developed in DAEMON, considering the adoption of part of the DAEMON solutions within their networks.</p> <p>Moreover, the analysis of operators' dataset by using DAEMON components provided useful insights for the design and dimensioning of OTE's networks, as well as to achieve optimal orchestration of the available resources.</p> <p>Currently, OTE explores new business models for NI that would allow the company to perform the technological transfer for the solution to the interested business unit. The related DAEMON-based solutions provide significant advantages for the company, especially for offering competitive solutions that could facilitate the market transition towards a real environment.</p> <p>Moreover, OTE presented DAEMON results in Infocom World 2023 forum, with top industrial audience, meant to foster further collaboration with on relevant topics.</p> <p>Last but not least, the collaboration among OTE and DAEMON's partners carries on as part of new research projects.</p>

4.1.3 Small and medium enterprises

Table 20. Exploitation plan for small and medium enterprises.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
ZSCALE	<p>ZSCALE has supported the distributed data management and decentralized monitoring infrastructure, within the DAEMON project, leveraging the Eclipse Zenoh opensource project. DAEMON's monitoring platform and its interfaces with high-speed data processing have had an impact on the evolutions of this product. Part of DAEMON innovations in decentralized monitoring of infrastructure have been fed into the open-source project Eclipse Zenoh.</p>

	<p>At the beginning of the DAEMON project, January 2021, the Eclipse Zenoh project had 100 stars in its github repository and it was in version v0.5.0-beta. By the end of DAEMON project, the Eclipse Zenoh project has 1.1K stars in github repository, its current version is v0.10.1-rc (release candidate) and it is expected to come out with the version zenoh-v1.0 by April, 2024. Which will bring the project out of the incubation phase. The next step is to certify parts of the code.</p>
SRS	<p>SRS has provided and assisted partners in using its open-source 4G and 5G RAN solutions, namely srsRAN 4G and srsRAN Project. In doing so it has allowed SRS to push forward its UE and gNodeB solutions, specifically its new O-RAN compliant 5G SA gNB - srsRAN Project. The activities carried out in DAEMON have allowed for the testing and strengthening of the SRS 5G product portfolio. This has then been fed back to the open-source community, with work stemming from the project impacting releases of both srsRAN 4G and srsRAN Project.</p> <p>Work from activities within the project such as the development of Nubery in Activity A1 (D3.3 [12], Section 3.1; D5.3 , Section 3.2.1) and the use of srsRAN in Testbed 6 in D5.3[14] has led to multiple bug fixes in srsRAN 4G as reported in D6.3[3] Working with partners during the course of the project and assisting them in modifying the codebase locally has been fed back to the open-source community in releases of srsRAN 4G during the lifecycle of DAEMON.</p> <p>SRS has also assisted in promoting the project physically at events such as ICC 2023 and MWC 2023. These industry events have been used to further the impact of the project's results. Exposing new audiences to the project and its outcomes beyond those focused on research.</p> <p>During the DAEMON Industry Workshop held in TID's premises in Barcelona the SRS CEO, Paul Sutton, gave a presentation discussing the ongoing development of srsRAN 4G and srsRAN Project. This presentation also highlighted how work carried out in DAEMON had assisted in the development of the codebase of both projects.</p> <p>As SRS continues to develop and harden srsRAN Project, it is expected that contributions from DAEMON to standards bodies like O-RAN and 3GPP, and work based on the project, will continue to impact the products development roadmap.</p>
WINGS	<p>WINGS (WINGS ICT Solutions) is an innovations company that develops end-to-end digital solutions and transformation for vertical business sectors; Environment (air quality, natural disasters), Utilities and Infrastructures (energy/water/gas, transportation, construction), Production & Manufacturing (food, factories/logistics), Service Sectors (health, education/culture, government, security/defense), as well as Smart Cities. WINGS will leverage DAEMON developments, specifically with regards to AI-powered optimisations for cloud-native environments, advanced service orchestration mechanisms leveraging Conflict resolution capabilities, and Federated Learning-powered Anomaly detection, to optimise its service and products offering for verticals in the context of beyond 5G and 6G in the areas of Industry 4.0 (interactive mobile robots), environmental/civil mission critical services and e-Health.</p>

4.1.4 Academic and research centers

Table 21. Exploitation for academia and research centers.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
IMDEA	<p>IMDEA has supported the transfer of the technology developed within the DAEMON to the industrial sector in a number of ways during the action lifetime. Most of these efforts have been built around the solutions for line-rate inference based on user-plane machine learning integration developed within the context of Activity A18 (D3.3, Section 6.1; D5.3, Section 3.8.3), and are outlined next.</p> <p>First, the solutions for line-rate inference have been implemented and demonstrated through an experimental testbed consisting of industry-grade 32-port 100-Gbps programmable switches equipped with Barefoot Tofino chipsets and dedicated servers fully interconnected at 100 Gbps.</p> <p>Second, IMDEA has communicated the results of the experiments carried out within DAEMON and with the platform above to Intel, through the official channels opened by the Intel Connectivity Research Program and of the Intel Connectivity Academy; Intel has approved the outcomes and also awarded them a 2022 Fast Forward Initiative recognition.</p>

	<p>Third, the aforementioned solutions have been demonstrated at a leading global industry event like the 2023 Mobile World Congress, ensuring wide exposure to the relevant industry players worldwide.</p> <p>Fourth, the same solutions were demonstrated at the first industry workshop of DAEMON, which was held in the Barcelona premises of Telefonica with substantial industry presence, as well as at international conferences such as IEEE INFOCOM or IEEE NetSoft, which also attract industry presence; in the case of IEEE NetSoft, the demonstrator won the Best Demo award of the conference.</p> <p>In addition to the above, DAEMON allowed IMDEA to recruit and train 2 new PhD students and 2 postdoctoral fellows, creating new expertise at the interface of machine learning and mobile networking critical to European industry. These early-stage and junior researchers grew substantial competences on the activities outlined above, as well as on loss meta-learning and hybrid learning and optimization in Activities 20, 21, 22, 32 and 33 (D4.3, Section 4; D5.3, Section 3.6).</p>
IMEC	<p>IMEC has supported the transfer of the technology developed and knowledge within the DAEMON to the industrial and academic sector in several ways during the action lifetime.</p> <p>At research level, the scientific knowledge produced by DAEMON, as well as the collaborations with the academic and industry members of the consortium, has contributed to strengthening the position of IMEC as one of the key partners in Belgium and Europe with knowledge in AI-native, programable and flexible network architectures in Belgium and Europe. The recently started JU SNS 6G-TWIN project, where IMEC is leading the network architectural work package, and BEL6GICA, a concerted research project, supported by FOD Economie, K.M.O., Middenstand en Energie of Belgium, aiming at establishing landscape and roadmap for 6G in Belgium, have been very much affected by the outcomes from DAEMON, specifically due to the knowledge acquired by leading the AI-Native architectural design in DAEMON and their research activities (D2.3, Section 3-6), represented in 4 published papers and 2 more submitted at this point in time.</p> <p>Additionally, IMEC has strength its role in the topic of AI, where a new portfolio of solutions is being built for the telco and network industry, specifically on AI-assisted functionalities across the radio (Activity A12, with latest updates in D3.3 Section 4.2 and D5.3 Section 3.5.6), and both network (Activity A16, with latest updates in D4.3 Section 6.2 and D5.3 Section 3.5.5) and service stack (Activities A11, with latest updates in D3.3 Section 4.1 and D5.3 Section 3.5.7). Another example of such recognition is hosting the 2024 EuCNC&6G summit in Antwerp (IMEC branch in this project), which recognize our role in shaping the future of 6G and beyond networks.</p> <p>At teaching and training, the results and research activities of DAEMON have been already introduced in two master courses in the department of computer sciences of the University of Antwerp. The first course that have been shaped with research outcomes from DAEMON is <i>Topics in computers networks</i>, where topics related to orchestration of intelligence (WP2, architectural design evolving from D2.1 up to D2.3), ai-assisted network management and control ((research from A11, A12, and A16), has been introduced. Similarly, the course of <i>Internet of Things</i> has been enhanced to introduce novel topics in the topic of resource efficient ML for AI (D2.3, Section).</p> <p>Similarly, the innovation of DAEMON has sparked new research topics that have been translated in new positions for PhD and master students in the University of Antwerp under the new research programs of Network Intelligence and Perceptive Radios (both under development). Finally, part of the knowledge of DAEMON (edge orchestration from activities A11 and A16, 5G trials in verticals such as connected vehicles from activity A11) will be thought in a new post-graduated course called "The ABC of 5G Technical, Business and Regulation Perspectives", which has been recently launched as a collaboration between the University of Antwerp, Gent University, and Vrije Universiteit Brussel.</p>
UMA	<p>UMA has supported the transfer of the technology developed and knowledge within DAEMON to different sectors during its action lifetime.</p> <p>The scientific knowledge produced by DAEMON, as well as the collaborations with the academic and industry members of the consortium, has contributed to strengthening the position of UMA as one of the leaders in pushing the development and dynamic deployment of energy efficient Beyond 5G software and virtual network functionality.</p>

	<p>As a post-consequence, UMA acquired national funding for the new project 'IRIS: Stepwise configuratlon of virtualized Services for sustainable and adaptive mobile networks', which extends research problems and solutions motivated by the complete work in DAEMON. Additionally, UMA continues as a member of TASOVA+, the nationally funded network specialized on new trend to automatically analyze and optimize software, including the trade-off of runtime and energy consumption. Regarding dissemination, UMA accomplished many top-tier publications like Journal of Systems and Software, Knowledge-Based Systems, IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering, Information and Software Technology, Software and Systems Modeling and Journal of Network and Computer Applications, and indexed conferences like ACM SPLC, CAiSE and ICSR. Finally, all these results have been reported throughout the deliverables D2.3, D3.3, D4.3, D5.2 and summarized in D1.3 and D6.3.</p> <p>DAEMON provided UMA with the access to many systems and energy measurement data to exploit their newly developed approached and running tools, and, as a consequence, the results can be directly applied to industrial solutions. Furthermore, 3 of these tools are available to use and have been registered with their respective copyright ID (i.e., NEMO, SAVRUS and RHEA).</p> <p>Finally, DAEMON has been instrumental in elevating the teaching quality, research capabilities, and overall academic environment within the CAOSD group at UMA, positioning it as a hub for innovation and excellence in telematics. For instance, the meticulous work on the DAEMON dynamic reasoning (as documented in D3 and D4) allowed UMA to include real uses cases when optimizing networks virtualized functionality wrt performance, energy consumption and cost, especially, but not only, in the courses included in UMA MSc. in Software Engineering and AI.</p> <p>In the course of the project, and besides the main team, 1 PhD Student, 1 MSc. Student and 2 graduate students have been recruited and trained in UMAs solutions to DAEMON. One of them, performed a short research stay in the TUD consortium partner facilities to retrieve energy consumption metrics and readings from TUD algorithms. Additionally, 1 International PhD Thesis directly related to WP3 and WP5 has been delivered with Distinction, another one related to WP3, WP4 and DWP5 has been accepted and is waiting for the defense date, and 1 MSc. Thesis has been delivered with the maximum grade.</p>
<p>UC3M</p>	<p>UC3M exploits its participation in DAEMON along several axes, as discussed next. The DAEMON project has enabled UC3M to further improve its research quality, continuously targeting top-tier publications like ACM Mobicom, IEEE Infocom, and IEEE JSAC, universally considered premier forums in telecommunications engineering. This has been enabled by the collaborations within the DAEMON consortium, encompassing academia and industry partners. All the scientific publications that contributed to this role have been reported throughout the WP3 deliverables D3.1, D3.2, D3.3. More in details the work reported in Section 3.1 and 3.2 of D3.3, attached to activities Activities A1 and A29, that have been published into top tier venues.</p> <p>Such collaboration contributes to creating the high-standing UC3M profile as a leading European institution in next-generation mobile network research. This dynamic creates a virtuous cycle, bolstering UC3M's attractiveness for future industry collaborations, either through public funding or direct partnerships. During the project, UC3M was lead editor of the book on 6G published in the context of the Arch WG, as reported in Section 2.2.1 of this document.</p> <p>Furthermore, DAEMON participation facilitates offering research-oriented positions to recent graduates, particularly in forward-looking fields like artificial intelligence and mobile networking. These graduates either advance UC3M's academic excellence or join the industry, reinforcing Europe's leadership in 6G technology. The work on one PhD student contributed to the deliverables, especially D5.3 on the evaluation activities, related to activities A1 and A29, as well as, the quantum evaluation activities reported in the same document.</p> <p>DAEMON contributions improve UC3M educational commitment. The project's insights have enriched course materials, positively impacting both existing and potential new academic programs. For instance, students in telematics and telecommunications engineering, but also those enrolled in the 5G Master's program, benefit directly from these enhancements. For instance, the work on the DAEMON architecture reported in D2.1, D2.2, and D2.3 allowed to improve the quality of the material related to the Master on 5G Network that UC3M is currently offering. For instance, the work on the</p>

	<p>network data analytics reported in Section 10.6 of D2.1 has served as a basis for updating the material of the course Core Network in 5G, already in the 21/22, 22/23, and 22/24 edition of the master.</p> <p>Additionally, the knowledge of topics investigated by DAEMON allows UC3M to consider new degree or master programs at the intersection of diverse fields, like artificial intelligence with mobile networking or quantum computing. This interdisciplinary approach attracts students from varied backgrounds, fostering a generation of engineers with highly sought-after market skills. The knowledge gained during the design of WP3 algorithms allowed to create a new degree on Artificial Intelligence that is starting soon. For instance, the work on explainability reported in Section 3.2 of D3.3, attached to activity A29 allowed UC3M to experiment with novel tools in Artificial Intelligence under a topic that address Values such as the trustworthiness of the decisions taken by Artificial Intelligence.</p>
<p>TUD</p>	<p>TUD has the following exploitation plans for the results and learnings from DAEMON.</p> <p>The scientific knowledge produced by DAEMON, as well as the collaborations with the academic and industry members of the consortium, have contributed to strengthening the position of TU Delft as one of the leaders in Beyond-5G Networks in the Netherlands and Europe. Practical results of this include, most notably, the acquisition of national funding for a flagship 6-years 6G project (starting 2024) that TU Delft is leading, and which includes many Dutch universities and industries.</p> <p>The research agenda of this project is heavily affected by DAEMON and will pursue research problems motivated by the work in DAEMON. For instance, Activities A4 (D4.3, Sec. 3.3) and A5 (D4.3, Sec. 3.4) allowed us to study, implement and evaluate novel RAN energy-saving techniques, and will serve as starting point for the design of scalable and fair energy-prudent resource control policies for O-RAN in the above follow-up project. Besides, TUD's expertise on energy-aware policies has benefited from the pertinent activities of other partners such as UMA, e.g., see A6 (D3.3, Sec. 4.3), A15 (D5.1, Sec. 3.2.4) and A26 (D4.1, Sec. 3.1.3).</p> <p>Additionally, the collaborations of TU Delft with the industry partners of DAEMON have increased our capabilities in using testbeds and in data-driven evaluations, and we plan to leverage these for conducting, henceforth, more systems and experimental work. For example, evaluations results reported in D5.2 Sec. 4.2.1 and D5.3 Section 3.3.2 are such instances, and we plan to incorporate them in our local testbeds in the DoloT fieldlab (https://doiotfieldlab.tudelftcampus.nl/). Furthermore, TUD plans to build upon the architecture innovations of DAEMON, such as activities A1 (D3.2, Sec. 2.1) and A2 (D3.3, Sec. 3.3) and propose new algorithmic toolboxes that exploit their potential for performance and cost improvements.</p> <p>The results and activities of DAEMON have been already used to improve courses such as Real-time Systems and HighPerformance Data Networking. Namely, we have updated the course material to include the latest developments in AI/ML methods for network control, recent advancements in programmability and controllability of core networks, and so on. In this context, activities such as A20 (D4.1, Sec. 3.1, 4.1), A29 (D3.3, Sec. 3.2), and A33 (D4.3, Sec. 3.3.1.2) that tailor fundamental AI/ML models for key networking problems will serve as ideal course material.</p> <p>Furthermore, TU Delft will explore the potential of organizing new courses based on the results of DAEMON, such as a special course on AI/ML algorithms for resource management, building on the content in activities such as A10 and A11. Initial material for this course was prepared for seminars and summer school activities during DAEMON's execution. Finally, DAEMON has offered the opportunity to several early-career researchers (PhD level) to obtain hands-on experience in B5G problems, and training (by industry partners) on using testbeds and/or working with real-world operational datasets. This skillset will be further transferred to other PhD and M.Sc. students towards expanding their knowledge regarding B5G/6G networks.</p>

4.2 Exploitation plan of products and platforms for vendors and SMEs

In Table 22, a detailed description of the platform and products for vendors and SMEs according to the exploitation plan is reported.

Table 22. Exploitation for vendors and SMEs.

Partner	Product or platform	Description of impact on platform/product	DAEMON innovation area
NEC	NEC O-RAN product portfolio	NEC's RAN Intelligent Controllers for O-RAN Compatible RANs will be highly benefited with the outcome of DAEMON's research. The objective is to derive data collection and decision-making entities both at near-real-time and non-real-time timescales as a consequence of Activities A4 and A5.	RAN orchestration
	NEC 5G vRAN platform	NEC plans to exploit the results of Activities A1 and A2 to improve NEC's RAN virtualization platforms.	RAN virtualization
	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	NEC will use the results of Activity A23 to open a new product line on smart reflectors.	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
NBL	Digital Operations Center	The Digital Operations Center (DOC), which allows to expose the rich capabilities of a network as consumable services to tenants, benefits from the DAEMON results. The DAEMON results around self-learning MANO, i.e., 1) the activity A30 around intelligent placement of VNFs, 2) the activity A16 dealing with algorithms for vertical scaling of VNFs and 3) the result reported in D6,1, Table 1, 5 th entry providing a method for SLA decomposition, improves the service orchestration, service operations and service assurance algorithms of DOC.	End-to-end orchestrator
	CloudBand product family	The CloudBand (CB) product family, consisting of an NFV resource and network service orchestrator built for OpenStack and VMware, is impacted by the DAEMON results. Similar as in the case of the DOC, activity A30 around placing VNFs and activity 16 around scaling up/down and in/out, will be important to improve the algorithms that administer, monitor, and optimize NFV infrastructure resources across geographically distributed NFV infrastructure nodes. The results pertaining to the energy-aware placement and close-loop control are expected to impact the (future) list of features of the CloudBand product family.	End-to-end orchestrator
	FlowOne	The research carried out in DAEMON allows enhancing FlowOne, which provides an agile and modular orchestration for managing service orchestration (activity A30) across virtualized and hybrid networks.	Edge orchestrator
	Altiplano	The research carried out in the DAEMON project helps to further develop the AI/ML components in Altiplano, which manages Software Defined Access Networks (SDANs). For example, Altiplano can detect if a Passive Optical Network (PON) user produces much more traffic than a normal user, based on a technique similar to the traffic classification algorithm of activity A3.	Fixed access management solution
WINGS	AIRWINGS	Product platform regarding Air Quality. It includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. AIRWINGS product will be impacted by the DAEMON results. In detail, the federated learning powered	Federated Learning powered

		anomaly detection solution designed in WP4 and prototyped in WP5 (activity A9) will be integrated with the AI algorithms developed in the product in order to improve the AI performance.	Anomaly Detection
	ARTEMIS	Product platform regarding Utilities. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solution designed in WP4 and prototyped in WP5 (activity A9) will be integrated with the ARTEMIS AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
	AQUAWINGS	Product platform regarding Aquaculture. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solutions of DAEMON (activity A9) will improve the performance of AQUAWINGS AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
	STARLIT	Product platform regarding the Health sector. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solutions of DAEMON (Activity A9) will improve the performance of STARLIT AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
ZSCALE	Eclipse Zenoh	Eclipse Zenoh provides a protocol suite for adaptive and distributed data-sharing, to enhance data distribution and flexibility. DAEMON monitoring platform and its interfaces with high-speed data processing can have an impact on the evolutions of this product. Part of DAEMON innovations in decentralized monitoring of infrastructure such as activity A13 data-driven resource orchestration where edge and cloud orchestrator acts as a subscriber for various types of data that can be stored on edges, and used for training or online learning/optimization, used in T4 Smart Highway. Such innovations will be fed into the open-source project Eclipse Zenoh and will be used later in other domains such as robotics or software defined vehicles.	Distributed data-management and decentralized monitoring infrastructure
SRS	srsRAN	srsRAN 4G is a fully open-source 4G and 5G-prototyping suite including complete UE, RAN, and Core network implementations. Over the course of the project features were added and mainlined to the open-source codebase based on work and feedback from partners (specifically, feedback from activities A1, A4, A5, A24, A29). This also helped to create the foundations for the srsRAN Project codebase which is the open-source O-RAN compliant 5G SA gNB developed by SRS. This was provided to project partners during 2023, and replaced srsRAN 4G as the recommended 5G RAN platform. As DAEMON closes, srsRAN Project will continue to be developed and updated. Due to srsRAN Project being O-RAN compliant, its features and development are directly influenced by both the O-RAN and 3GPP specifications. As a result, contributions from DAEMON to these SDOs will continue to have an impact on the development of the codebase long after the project closes. This will have impacts for not only the open-source community, but also other publicly funded projects and commercial networks that utilize srsRAN Project.	RAN Orchestration

4.3 Exploitation plan for datasets and open-source software

The DAEMON consortium will foster adoption of the datasets generated in the project and open-source software produced in the project beyond the lifetime of the action.

4.3.1 End-of-project social media campaign

The project will launch a comprehensive social media campaign during March and April 2024 so as to communicate the contributions of DAEMON that are available to the research community. Specifically, we have already disseminated via social media as of March 2024 the open-source preprints of scientific publication that DAEMON made available in Zenodo.¹³ We are continuing this campaign by announcing the entirety of the open-source artifacts associated to activities of the DAEMON consortium, including all the contributions we have already open-sourced in the project Github, and briefly explaining how the software and datasets can be used by the scientific and industry community to advance research and innovation in the design and validation of NI for 6G systems.

4.3.2 Legacy of the DAEMON NI Plane

The proposal for a new Network Intelligence (NI) Plane conceived by DAEMON has already had an impact of activities external to the project that will also continue once DAEMON has ended. The NI Plane concept and design has influenced the vision for 6G-ready architectural models that was shaped by 5G PPP and is now inherited by 6G IA. Specifically, as detailed Section 3 of deliverable D2.3 of DAEMON, 5G PPP and 6G IA have embraced the concept of the Network Intelligence Stratum [19] as an integral part of the holistic architectural framework originally developed by the 5G Architecture Working Group of 5G PPP, as illustrated in Figure 25 below and reported in the whitepaper “6G Architecture Landscape – European perspective” [20]. This ensure that **the contributions of DAEMON in terms of advancing the 6G architectural model towards a native integration of AI will have a continued impact well beyond the scope of the action itself and will help shaping the European proposals for future-generation mobile networks.**

Figure 25. The architectural framework proposed by the 5GPPP Arch WG [20].

In addition, the DAEMON project also defined the internal NIP organization and operations, introducing a suitable reference representation of complex NI algorithms as a hierarchy of Network Intelligence Services (NISs) that can be broken down into one or more Network Intelligence Functions (NIFs), which, in turn, are composed of atomic NIF Components (NIF-Cs) [21]. As part of its activities, DAEMON specified management procedures for NISs and NIFs by a Network Intelligence Orchestration (NIO) and outlined a proposal for an internal structure of the fundamental building blocks and interfaces of the NIO.

All these specifications are already being leveraged beyond the boundaries of the DAEMON action, as they have been adopted by other large collaborative projects in the European Union landscape. For example, the ETHER project (<https://www.ether-project.eu/>), funded by the Horizon Europe SNS JU 2022 Stream B call, is employing the NIP and NIO representations of DAEMON as the reference approach to deploy AI/ML solutions that empower smart hybrid Terrestrial Networks / Non-Terrestrial Networks (TN/NTN) in their planned ETHER end-to-end architecture, and are also adopting the N-MAPE-K approach to model NIS in the target system. In a similar way, the ORIGAMI project (<https://sns-origami.eu/>), funded by the Horizon Europe SNS JU 2023 Stream B call, is employing the DAEMON NIP as a cornerstone on top of which to develop their innovative 6G architectural layers that enable global cross-operator functionalities.

The fact that the DAEMON specifications are fertilizing follow-up research projects ensures its long-lasting impact on shaping future research on the architectural models of 6G infrastructures.

¹³ <https://twitter.com/h2020daemon>

4.3.3 NetMob 2023 Data Challenge dataset

In addition, the project will push for making openly available the highly original dataset that empowered the NetMob 2023 Data Challenge, whose organization was also supported by the DAEMON project. This is a unique dataset that offers a rare opportunity to the multidisciplinary research community to access rich data about the spatiotemporal consumption of mobile applications in a developed country. The generation process of the dataset sets a new quality standard, leading to information about the demands generated by 68 popular mobile services, geo-referenced at a high resolution of 100x100 m² over 20 metropolitan areas in France, and monitored during 77 consecutive days.

The generation process underpinning the dataset hinges upon open-source geospatial data and extensive measurements from a major mobile network operator in France that collaborates with DAEMON partners. We note that the operator roughly has a 30% market penetration in the country that is relatively uniform across the French territory. This provides a solid statistical basis for downstream analyses that generalize to the entirety of the local population.

Figure 26. Mobile services whose traffic are present in the NetMob 2023 Data challenge dataset, ranked by the fraction of total demand they generate.

This dataset sets a new standard for mobile network data made available to the research community, from multiple perspectives. First, the dataset contains information about the data traffic generated by the mobile devices attached to a modern 4G/3G cellular network, whereas openly available datasets typically cover Call Detail Records in 2G/3G networks. Second, the dataset captures traffic in a developed country like France, which offers a different perspective than earlier datasets focusing on developing countries. Third, the data spans 20 metropolitan areas, offering the possibility of generalizing analyses and juxtaposing results across heterogeneous urbanization levels and population densities. Fourth, the dataset offers rich information about the usage of 68 popular mobile services, which opens significant opportunities to understand the consumption of applications and its implications across research domains: Figure 26 offers a look into the applications included in the dataset, and a ranking of the same based on the fraction of total traffic they generate.

4.3.4 Zenoh open-source software adoption initiatives

Eclipse Zenoh adoptions initiatives span different domains outside of the Networking Intelligence domain. Those initiatives include automotive, robotics, and Cloud-Edge and IoT domains.

- Eclipse Zenoh was identified as the most appropriate protocol for V2X applications for autonomous and assisted driving in the IUT-T FGAI4AD-01 Automated driving safety data protocol – Specification [22].
- Eclipse Zenoh has been selected as one of the communication middleware in addition to MQTT, in the Eclipse Software Defined Vehicle (SDV) working group [23].
- The Open Source Robotics Foundation performed a study and concluded that Zenoh best meets the requirements, and will be chosen as an alternative middleware. Zenoh was also the most-recommended alternative by ROS/ROS2 users [24].
- Eclipse Zenoh, the zenoh-plugin-dds was used in the Autonomous Indy Challenge 2021 to provides the IAC racecar's vehicle-to-everything (V2X) and swarming capability. It does this by bridging Open Robotics' ROS 2 DDS over Cisco's Ultra-Reliable Wireless Backhaul to track-side race control and chase vehicles. Eclipse zenoh's ROS 2 DDS topic filtering allows teams to choose which topics are propagated over the radio [25].
- Eclipse Zenoh was presented in the Eclipse SDV Community Day, EclipseCon, and RosCon conferences in the last two years.

Additionally, ZSCALE has been identified as one of the top 20 startups in vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communication, to be watched in 2024 out of 509 startups analyzed [26].

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